

**Data-Driven Estimation of Ship
Manoeuvring Hydrodynamic Derivatives
using a Hybrid MARUS–PINN Framework
with LLM-Guided Symbolic Discovery**

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This dissertation does NOT contain confidential material and thus
can be made available to staff and students via the library.

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Abstract

Identification of hydrodynamic derivatives that govern ship manoeuvring behaviour for autonomous vessels such as unmanned surface vehicles (USVs) is essential for diverse maritime purposes including oceanographic research, environmental monitoring, and autonomous navigation. However, conventional hydrodynamic modelling approaches, such as classical manoeuvring models, experimental methods, and high-fidelity computational fluid dynamics (CFD), are often labour-intensive, costly, and time-consuming, and their estimated parameters may not fully capture real-world operating conditions due to nonlinearities, scale effects, and complex sea states. With the advent of machine learning, recent advances in Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs) offer a promising alternative by embedding governing fluid-dynamic equations directly into the neural learning network, providing the advantages of data-driven learning while maintaining physical consistency. Hence, this thesis investigates a novel approach that combines Marine Robotics Unity Simulator (MARUS)–simulated manoeuvring data, PINN-based parameter learning, and symbolic discovery via Large Language Models (LLMs) to estimate hydrodynamic derivatives with improved robustness, reduced data requirements, and enhanced interpretability compared to conventional system identification methods, while promoting interoperability and standardization through its modular design.

To evaluate this hybrid approach, the thesis addresses the following research question: Can a hybrid MARUS–PINN–LLM framework provide more accurate, interpretable, and data-efficient estimates of manoeuvring hydrodynamic derivatives than conventional system identification methods? To this end, an extensive set of experiments and ablation studies is conducted to compare the proposed hybrid model with its purely data-driven and purely physics-based counterparts across parameter accuracy, trajectory reconstruction quality, and generalization to diverse maneuvering conditions of various industry-standard USVs. The results demonstrate that integrating symbolic discovery with PINNs reduces sway-acceleration error by 86%, yaw-rate acceleration error by 66%, and heading-rollout error by 89% relative to purely data-driven baselines, producing compact, physically consistent residual terms that align with established nonlinear hydrodynamic effects while its physics-only counterparts catastrophically diverge from the ground-truths. Taken together, these findings highlight the potential of hybrid physics–machine-learning frameworks to advance the estimation of manoeuvring coefficients for the next generation of autonomous marine systems.

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Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIS	Automatic Identification System
AITs	AI Transparency Statement
ANN	Artificial Neural Network
AUV	Autonomous Underwater Vehicle
BEM	Boundary Element Method
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
CI	Confidence Interval
CMT	Circular Motion Test
CNLS	Constrained Nonlinear Least Squares
DDS	Data Distribution Service
DMD	Dynamic Mode Decomposition
DOF	Degrees of Freedom
DT	Digital Twin
EKF	Extended Kalman Filter
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FMI	Functional Mock-up Interface
FMU	Functional Mock-up Unit
GNC	Guidance, Navigation, and Control
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GP	Gaussian Process

GPS	Global Positioning System
gRPC	gRPC Remote Procedure Calls
HIL	Hardware-in-the-Loop
HLA	High Level Architecture
IMO	International Maritime Organization
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
ITTC	International Towing Tank Conference
LPP	Length Between Perpendiculars
LLM	Large Language Model
LS-SVR	Least Squares Support Vector Regression
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
MAD	Median Absolute Deviation
MARUS	Marine Robotics Simulator
MCMC	Markov Chain Monte Carlo
ML	Machine Learning
MLP	Multi-Layer Perceptron
MMG	Maneuvering Modeling Group
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
MSE	Mean Squared Error
OOD	Out-of-Distribution
OTT	Oblique Towing Test
PDE	Partial Differential Equation
PINN	Physics-Informed Neural Network
PMM	Planar Motion Mechanism
PRBS	Pseudo-Random Binary Sequence
PSD	Power Spectral Density
RANS	Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes

RB	Rigid Body
RLS	Recursive Least Squares
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
ROS	Robot Operating System
ROV	Remotely Operated Vehicle
RPM	Revolutions Per Minute
RTS	Rauch-Tung-Striebel
SI	System Identification
SIL	Software-in-the-Loop
SR	Symbolic Regression
SVM	Support Vector Machine
SVR	Support Vector Regression
TC	Turning Circle
UKF	Unscented Kalman Filter
USV	Unmanned Surface Vehicle
WEC	Wave Energy Converter
ZZ	Zig-Zag

Chapter 1

Introduction

Covering over 70% of the Earth's surface (65% open ocean, 6% coastal ocean), the global oceans are vast, unconfined environments whose magnitude and dynamism have necessitated the development of a broad spectrum of marine vehicles for purposes of exploration, transportation, and commerce. These vehicles span a wide range from massive cargo ships, which move over 80% of the world's trade volume and are considered the backbone of international commerce (United Nations Conference on Trade and Development, 2024), to specialized oceanographic research vessels conducting deep-sea exploration. More recently, autonomous surface and underwater vehicles (AUVs, USVs, ROVs) have been deployed for scientific, commercial, defense, and environmental monitoring domains, reflecting the wide marine craft spectrum illustrated in Fig. 1.1 (J. Xu et al., 2024; Bae and Hong, 2023).

Figure 1.1: Spectrum of marine vehicles (Fossen, 2021).

Understanding and predicting how these vessels move through water requires knowledge of hydrodynamics, the study of how fluid forces and moments act on rigid bodies in motion. In the maritime context, hydrodynamic models produce mathematical representations of the interactions, allowing us to predict how a vessel might respond to currents, waves, control signals, and environmental disturbances (Fossen, 2021). Regardless of their form or function, enabling safe, efficient, and autonomous manoeuvring of marine vessels depends fundamentally on the accuracy of hydrodynamic models, which facilitate the prediction of a ship’s behaviour under varying operating conditions for critical maritime technologies such as navigational safety, energy efficiency, vessel design optimization, simulator-based crew training, autonomous vessel control, and environmental sustainability.

Historically, estimating the hydrodynamic coefficients required for modeling autonomous vessels has relied on physics-based formulations: equations derived from first principles of fluid mechanics offered interpretable parameters that provided physical insight into ship behavior but required extensive experimental undertakings, such as captive model tests or sea trials, to determine the many hydrodynamic derivatives. The result is a trade-off: while physics-first methods provide high fidelity in terms of their parameter estimations, they are costly, labor-intensive, time-consuming, and unfit for rapid prototyping or real-time applications.

From the early 2000s onward, system identification (SI) gained prominence as an alternative to traditional physics-based approaches. SI uses input–output algorithms to infer model parameters directly from measured maneuvering data by minimizing model–data errors, hence reducing reliance on costly and exhaustive physical experiments such as captive model tests (PMM, CMT, OTT). Unlike physical captive methods, which measure forces and moments in controlled tank environments, SI estimates hydrodynamic coefficients from the vessel’s motion responses during free-running manoeuvres. Yet, despite its appeal, SI still faces significant weaknesses: its estimates become unreliable when trial data are noisy or insufficient, given its highly data-intensive nature, and its linear assumptions often fail under strongly nonlinear maneuvering conditions at sea (H. Xu and Guedes Soares, 2025). These limitations highlight a recurring theme: models need to strike a balance between physical accuracy and data-driven flexibility, but neither system identification nor classical approaches completely achieve this.

Subsequently, an even more groundbreaking paradigm shift in determining hydrodynamic derivatives occurred with the advent of data-driven Machine Learning (ML) approaches (X. Chen et al., 2025; D. Liu et al., 2025). Black-box regression methods, ranging from simpler support vector machines to more advanced recurrent

and attention-based neural networks, now surpass prior models in their ability to extract nonlinear patterns directly from data. Their potential for online model adaptation as new data arrive promises transformative progress in real-time vessel modeling. Nonetheless, this rather impressive capability introduces new risks: black-box models inherently lack physical interpretability and often generalize poorly beyond the domain of their training data. In safety-critical maritime domains, where predictive accuracy can mean the difference between safe maneuvering and disaster, such limitations are no longer academic, but they threaten the trust, certification, and adoption on which the future depends. Taken together, traditional physics-based hydrodynamic models, SI approaches, and purely data-driven ML methods highlight a persistent limitation: no existing method provides a solution that is simultaneously accurate, interpretable, data-efficient, and robust across diverse manoeuvring conditions.

Classical Models	System Identification	Pure Data-Driven	Hybrid Framework
<i>First-principles / CFD</i>	<i>Input-Output Analysis</i>	<i>Black-box Regression</i>	<i>PINN + Symbolic LLM</i>
Advantages:	Advantages:	Advantages:	Advantages:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Physically meaningful ✓ High fidelity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Reduces captive testing ✓ Uses sea-trial data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Captures nonlinearity ✓ Online adaptability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Data-efficient ✓ Physically consistent
Limitations:	Limitations:	Limitations:	Research Goal:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> × Costly × Labour-intensive × Time-consuming 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> × Noise sensitive × Limited generalizability × Fails in high nonlinearity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> × Non-physical results × Lack of interpretability × Data-intensive 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ★ Accurate estimation ★ Interpretable discovery

Figure 1.2: Comparative analysis of hydrodynamic modeling approaches. The proposed hybrid framework aims to bridge the gap by combining accuracy with interpretability.

Consequently, the recent research frontier has primarily focused on hybrid modelling approaches that integrate physics-based equations with data-driven learning, including methods such as physics-informed neural networks (PINNs). However, significant gaps still remain: existing hybrid models lack consistency in how physics-based constraints are embedded into data-driven components, and they provide little interpretability regarding the learned data-informed corrections. Moreover, there are very limited reports of high-fidelity marine simulators such as MARUS being used to generate controlled, noise-free manoeuvring datasets for hydrodynamic coefficient estimation; and there is almost no work on using large language models (LLMs) to discover interpretable residual physics within ship manoeuvring formulations. This forms a clear research opportunity for a highly accurate and interpretable hybrid framework.

Therefore, the aim of this thesis is to develop, implement, and evaluate a hybrid MARUS–PINN–LLM framework for estimating manoeuvring hydrodynamic derivatives for USVs that is accurate, interpretable, data-efficient, and generalizes reliably to different maneuvering conditions. The central research question guiding this work is:

Can a hybrid MARUS–PINN–LLM framework provide more accurate, interpretable, and data-efficient estimates of manoeuvring hydrodynamic derivatives than conventional physics-only or data-only methods?

Supporting research questions include:

- **RQ2:** To what extent can MARUS-generated manoeuvring data serve as a reliable and high-fidelity data source for estimating hydrodynamic derivatives, considering the costly nature of traditional experimental and CFD-based datasets?
- **RQ3:** Can LLM-guided symbolic discovery generate meaningful and physically consistent corrections to the physics-based manoeuvring equations?
- **RQ4:** How robust is the hybrid framework to noise, maneuver variability, and out-of-domain hydrodynamic data?

This thesis makes several contributions:

1. A novel hybrid MARUS–PINN–LLM framework that combines physics-based accuracy, convenient but high-fidelity simulation-generated data, and symbolic reasoning for hydrodynamic parameter estimation used in autonomous navigation for USVs.
2. A fully automated and open-source MARUS data generation and engineering tool that produces clean and validated datasets for hydrodynamic system identification.
3. A high-quality MARUS-generated dataset of IMO-compliant maneuvering trajectories for systematic hydrodynamic model development and evaluation.
4. An LLM-driven symbolic discovery system that outputs highly interpretable residual corrections to the classical physics-adopted maneuvering equations.
5. Evidence, through extensive ablation studies and testing experiments, that the proposed hybrid framework improves parameter accuracy, trajectory reconstruction, and generalisation relative to both classical and more recent counterparts.

The remainder of this thesis is structured as follows. Chapter 2 presents a comprehensive literature review covering classical hydrodynamic models, conven-

tional experimental and CFD-based estimation methods, system identification techniques, modern machine learning approaches, recent advances in hybrid grey-box and physics-informed modelling, and a thorough evaluation of modern marine simulators, culminating in the identification of key research gaps. Next, chapter 3 explains the proposed hybrid MARUS–PINN–LLM framework, including the MARUS data-generation and conditioning pipeline, the GreyBox PINN architecture, the symbolic regression system, and the LLM-based physical interpretation process. Subsequently, chapter 4 reports the empirical findings, including MARUS data validation, classical benchmarks, model training behaviour, symbolic discovery outcomes, comparative evaluations against other baseline models, extensive ablation studies, and generalization tests on unseen maneuvering data. Finally, chapter 5 discusses the implications of the results through a critical perspective, and outlines recommendations.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

This chapter reviews the theoretical and methodological knowledge underpinning maneuvering hydrodynamics and the estimation of hydrodynamic derivatives for USVs. It begins by introducing the governing 6-DOF equations of motion and the classification of coupled and uncoupled derivatives that shape vessel dynamics. The review then examines why these derivatives matter for vessel autonomy, before surveying the main estimation approaches, including classical physics-based methods, experimental and CFD techniques, system identification, modern machine learning models, and emerging hybrid physics–ML frameworks. The last section, however, includes a comprehensive analysis of modern marine simulators used for derivative estimation.

2.1 Equations of Motion

The dynamics of a vessel are commonly represented using the six-degrees-of-freedom (6-DOF) nonlinear maneuvering model (Fig. 2.1).

Figure 2.1: Six degrees of freedom (6-DOF) motions of a marine vessel: translational (surge, sway, heave) and rotational (roll, pitch, yaw) (Fossen, 2021).

A widely cited formulation is that of Fossen (Fossen, 2021), whose work has become a standard reference in marine vehicle dynamics; the compact equation shown below is adapted from his 6-DOF model:

$$\mathbf{M}\dot{\boldsymbol{\nu}} + \mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\nu})\boldsymbol{\nu} + \mathbf{D}(\boldsymbol{\nu})\boldsymbol{\nu} + \mathbf{g}(\boldsymbol{\eta}) = \boldsymbol{\tau} + \mathbf{w} \quad (2.1)$$

where:

- $\boldsymbol{\nu} = [u, v, w, p, q, r]^T$: body-fixed linear and angular velocities,
- $\boldsymbol{\eta} = [x, y, z, \phi, \theta, \psi]^T$: Earth-fixed position and orientation,
- \mathbf{M} : inertia matrix, which combines the vessel’s rigid-body mass and inertia with the added-mass terms caused by the surrounding water. In practice, \mathbf{M} determines how much the vessel resists acceleration in each DOF.
- $\mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\nu})$: Coriolis–centripetal matrix. These terms come from both the rigid-body motion and the added mass, and they depend on the vessel’s velocity. They account for the coupling effects and gyroscopic-like forces that appear when the vessel is translating and rotating at the same time.
- $\mathbf{D}(\boldsymbol{\nu})$: hydrodynamic damping matrix. This contains the linear and nonlinear drag contributions that oppose motion. Following Fossen, it represents viscous and vortex-induced effects that dissipate energy as the hull moves through water.
- $\mathbf{g}(\boldsymbol{\eta})$: hydrostatic restoring vector, which models how gravity and buoyancy act to bring the vessel back to an equilibrium position when it is displaced. These restoring forces and moments depend on the vessel’s orientation and vertical position.
- $\boldsymbol{\tau}$: control forces and moments generated by actuators such as propellers, rudders, thrusters, and control surfaces,
- \mathbf{w} : environmental disturbances (wind, waves, currents).

The coefficients embedded in \mathbf{M} , \mathbf{C} , and \mathbf{D} include the hydrodynamic derivatives, which quantify how the vessel responds dynamically in surge (u), sway (v), yaw (r), and the other degrees of freedom. Although these parameters are indispensable for achieving fidelity in model-based simulations and for the reliability of guidance, navigation, and control system design (Fossen, 2021), their estimation remains a persistent challenge since many derivatives are difficult to measure and context dependent.

2.2 Hydrodynamic Derivatives and Coupling

Building on the structure introduced above, hydrodynamic derivatives within the \mathbf{M} , \mathbf{C} , and \mathbf{D} system matrices, according to Fossen (2021), are categorized by their position, distinguishing between independent motion and coupled interaction effects:

- **Diagonal Terms (Self-Interaction):** These terms appear on the main diagonal and quantify the forces or moments generated by motion in the same degree of freedom. For example, X_u represents the linear surge damping force opposing surge velocity (u), and N_r represents the yaw damping moment opposing yaw rate (r).
- **Off-Diagonal Terms (Cross-Coupling):** These terms appear off the main diagonal and quantify the interaction between different degrees of freedom. Coupling emerges from two different physical sources:
 1. **Rigid-Body/Inertial Coupling:** Caused by the vessel's mass distribution and Coriolis–centripetal effects. For instance, the term mur appears in the sway equation representing a centripetal force produced by the combination of surge velocity (u) and yaw rate (r). These contributions are represented in the rigid-body matrices \mathbf{M}_{RB} and \mathbf{C}_{RB} .
 2. **Hydrodynamic Coupling:** Caused by fluid-hull interactions, where a motion in one mode generates fluid forces in another. For instance, Y_r describes the sway force generated by yawing (r), and N_v describes the yaw moment generated by swaying (v). These are captured in the added mass (\mathbf{M}_A) and hydrodynamic damping (\mathbf{D}) matrices.

Coupling is particularly important for maneuvering predictions because vessel dynamics are inherently nonlinear. Neglecting these coupled terms consistently reduces the accuracy and reliability of the maneuvering model, particularly during dynamic maneuvers like zig-zag or turning circle tests.

Table 2.1: Representative linear and nonlinear hydrodynamic derivatives (Fossen, 2021).

Derivative	Type	Physical Interpretation
X_u	Diagonal	Surge Damping: Linear resistance to forward motion.
Y_v	Diagonal	Sway Damping: Resistance to lateral drift.
N_r	Diagonal	Yaw Damping: Resistance to rotational turning.
Y_r	Off-Diagonal	Sway-Yaw Coupling: Hydrodynamic sway force generated by yaw rate.
N_v	Off-Diagonal	Yaw-Sway Coupling: Hydrodynamic yaw moment generated by sway velocity (critical for directional stability).
X_{vv}	Nonlinear	Sway-Induced Resistance: Added surge resistance due to drift angle.

2.2.1 Why Hydrodynamic Derivatives Matter

Hydrodynamic derivatives are essential for translating theoretical vessel dynamics into accurate and safe manoeuvring behaviour. As shown in Table 2.1, both diagonal and cross-coupled terms in the 3-DOF model depict how a ship responds in surge, sway, and yaw. Their importance emerges in two key aspects:

1. **Model fidelity.** Missing or inaccurate derivatives distort predicted vessel trajectories. Obreja et al., 2010 showed that tuning nonlinear hydrodynamic models with estimated derivatives improves experimental agreement, while H. Xu and Guedes Soares, 2022 showed how parameter errors propagate nonlinearly, amplifying trajectory deviations.
2. **Control design.** Control and guidance systems are equally vulnerable: Kahveci and Ioannou, 2013 proved that unmodelled hydrodynamic uncertainties degrade steering accuracy and stability, underscoring the role of reliable derivatives in robust control.

In summary, although the essential nature of hydrodynamic derivatives is indisputable, they remain notoriously difficult and costly to estimate: experimental PMM and free-running tests provide reliable data but are expensive and limited in scope (Obreja et al., 2010); CFD approaches offer high fidelity but require substantial computational resources (Shang et al., 2021); and system identification methods are sensitive to noise and often struggle to converge under nonlinear manoeuvring dynamics (H. Xu and Guedes Soares, 2022). Purely data-driven ML techniques can

improve predictive accuracy but sacrifice physical consistency and interpretability, whereas hybrid physics–ML approaches preserve physical structure while adapting to data (Papandreou et al., 2025).

2.3 Classical Maneuvering Models

Given the challenges in estimating hydrodynamic derivatives, it is essential to examine how classical modelling approaches have historically addressed hydrodynamic modelling. Classical manoeuvring models, derived from first principles, represent a vessel’s dynamics by combining rigid-body mechanics with hydrodynamic forces. These are often classified as parametric models: their structure is based on physics, but they rely on scalar coefficients (hydrodynamic derivatives) that must be estimated. Optimizing these models is an exhaustive process that is often labor-intensive and error-prone. This section offers a critical analysis of the main classical models.

2.3.1 Key Models and Their Contributions

Nomoto Model (1957). One of the earliest approaches, Nomoto’s K–T model abstracts yaw dynamics as a first- or second-order transfer function between rudder angle and yaw rate (Nomoto et al., 1957). Its strength lies in its extreme simplicity; however, it simplifies the sway–yaw coupling and ignores nonlinear lift effects. This restricts its applicability to course-keeping and small rudder inputs where the response remains linear (Yasukawa and Yoshimura, 2015).

Abkowitz Model (1960s–1980s). This “whole-ship” model represents hydrodynamic forces and moments using a Taylor series expansion. The forces are expressed as polynomial equations of the state variables (surge u , sway v , yaw rate r) and control inputs (Abkowitz, 1980). While the Abkowitz framework captures extensive nonlinear and cross-coupled effects, the number of derivatives grows rapidly with the polynomial order. This leads to over-parameterization (multicollinearity), where coefficients often lose clear physical meaning, complicating the identification process (H. Xu and Guedes Soares, 2025).

Maneuvering Modeling Group (MMG) Model (1970s–present). The MMG model, updated by Yasukawa and Yoshimura (2015), is a standard in maneuvering simulations. Its key innovation is the modular separation of hydrodynamic effects into three components: Hull (H), Propeller (P), and Rudder (R). The model computes total forces as the sum of these components while explicitly accounting for physical interactions such as wake effects among them. This offers better physical

insight than Abkowitz-style polynomials and allows for modular updates, such as recent extensions to shallow-water contexts (Ding et al., 2025). Nonetheless, MMG accuracy relies heavily on empirical interaction coefficients, which recent studies show are sensitive to modeling choices (C. Chen et al., 2022) and parameter uncertainties (Li et al., 2024).

Table 2.2: Comparison of representative classical hydrodynamic models.

Model	Concept	Coupling	Pros	Cons
Nomoto et al. (1957)	Linear yaw–rudder transfer function	Minimal	Extremely simple; ideal for autopilot tuning	Valid only for small angles; ignores sway–yaw interaction
Abkowitz (1980)	Taylor series expansion (Whole-ship)	Extensive	Captures complex nonlinear coupled behavior	High parameter count; risk of overfitting; opaque coefficients
Yasukawa and Yoshimura (2015)	MMG: Modular decomposition (H+P+R)	Moderate	Physically transparent; modular; industry standard	Relies on empirical interaction factors; sensitive tuning

Modern Adaptations of Classical Frameworks. Recent research has turned to merging these classical models as a way to alleviate the heavy estimation burden inherent in them. For example, Miyauchi et al. (2024) successfully bridged the gap between methods by combining Abkowitz-style expansions with the low-speed MMG model; this hybrid structure reduced the need for extensive vessel-specific data while remaining flexible enough to handle different actuator configurations. Other studies have focused on enhancing standard models with CFD. For instance, Yu et al. (2024) integrated CFD-derived coefficients into a 4-DOF MMG framework for ships with dual propulsion, effectively capturing the complex interactions between hull, propeller, and rudder. However, while these CFD-enhanced variants certainly improve estimation feasibility, they are not a silver bullet: their accuracy remains highly sensitive to specific vessel design choices, meaning the fundamental challenge of model calibration has been resolved only partially.

2.3.2 Strengths and Limitations

Classical manoeuvring models remain valuable for their physical interpretability: each coefficient corresponds to a clear hydrodynamic effect, supporting better hydrodynamic analysis and principled controller design. Their modular structure, such as MMG’s hull–propeller–rudder decomposition, also makes them suitable foundations for grey-box identification, and they continue to serve as reference models across shallow and restricted waters (Ding et al., 2025; Miyauchi et al., 2024).

Their main weakness, however, is the parameterisation and identifiability burden. Incorporating nonlinearities and coupling rapidly expands the coefficient set, introduces collinearity, and produces vessel and condition-specific estimates with high tuning cost. Many implementations therefore linearise and omit coupling for feasibility, sacrificing realism (Yasukawa and Yoshimura, 2015). Even fully coupled models remain highly sensitive to modelling choices and interaction assumptions, yielding wide variability in validation manoeuvres such as turning circles and zig-zag tests (Chen et al., 2022; Li et al., 2024). These limitations have motivated subsequent experimental and computational methods.

2.4 Conventional Estimation Methods for Hydrodynamic Derivatives

The classical manoeuvring models discussed in the previous section constitute the mathematical structure of determining ship dynamics through sets of hydrodynamic derivatives, but they do not state how these parameters should be obtained; they merely specify how they are used once known. As a result, the accuracy of any classical model, whether Nomoto, Abkowitz, or MMG, depends entirely on the availability of reliable derivatives through external methods. This creates a direct link between classical models and the conventional techniques used to populate them, including (i) experimental approaches such as captive tests (PMM, CMT, OTT) and free-running manoeuvres, and (ii) numerical methods based on computational fluid dynamics (CFD), referred to as virtual captive model tests (Du et al., 2022; Islam and Guedes Soares, 2018).

2.4.1 Captive Test Methods

Experimental approaches are still considered the traditional source of obtaining high-quality derivative estimates. Captive tests impose controlled motions on a scaled vessel model to measure hydrodynamic forces (2.2), providing reliable and

interpretable data for benchmarking purposes (Islam and Guedes Soares, 2018; Kim et al., 2015). They typically use:

- **Planar Motion Mechanism (PMM):** Captive test imposing controlled surge–sway–yaw motions to measure hydrodynamic forces.
- **Circular Motion Test (CMT):** Captive test forcing the model to follow a circular path at constant angular velocity to capture sway–yaw coupling motions.
- **Oblique Towing Test (OTT):** Captive test towing the model at a fixed drift angle to measure steady sway forces and yaw moments.

2.4.2 Free-Running Manoeuvring Trials

Free-running tests complement these by capturing full-system behavior using standard manoeuvres (2.3) such as turning circles and zig-zags (Mitsuyuki et al., 2024; Okuda et al., 2022). However, both methods are costly, time-consuming, and in some cases, weather-dependent.

Figure 2.2: Example of a captive test (PMM) in MARINTEK’s towing tank. The scaled ship model is coupled with a multi-actuator mechanism that imposes controlled surge–sway–yaw motions to measure hydrodynamic forces and moments.

Figure 2.3: Example of a free-running manoeuvring test using an instrumented ship model (NRC Institute for Ocean Technology, 2004).

2.4.3 CFD-Based Virtual Captive Model Tests

Over the past decade, however, Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) has become the primary alternative to physical captive and free-running tests. CFD is used to perform virtual captive model tests, in which numerical solvers replicate the same prescribed PMM or CMT motion patterns that are traditionally executed in a towing tank. Thus, tools such as OpenFOAM, naoe-FOAM-SJTU, and STAR-CCM+ can generate full Abkowitz or MMG coefficient sets directly from simulated flow dynamics (C. Chen et al., 2022; Dai and Li, 2019). In addition to reproducing captive tests, CFD also enables systematic parametric studies with varying water depth, hull geometry, or propulsion configuration that would be impractical or too costly to realise through physical experiments (Lin et al., 2024; Yu et al., 2024). Despite this flexibility, CFD-derived derivatives remain sensitive to numerical settings such as mesh quality, turbulence model choice, propeller/rudder modelling, and time-step set-up, introducing reproducibility challenges and systematic bias from run to run (C. Chen et al., 2022; Islam and Guedes Soares, 2018).

Figure 2.4: Example of a CFD flow-field visualisation used in virtual captive model tests, used to numerically simulate PMM/CMT motion patterns to obtain the hydrodynamic forces and moments required for Abkowitz/MMG coefficient estimation (C. Chen et al., 2022).

2.4.4 Comparative Summary of Conventional Methods

Collectively, captive tests, free-running trials, and CFD-based virtual captive simulations form the three mainstream methods used to estimate manoeuvring hydrodynamic derivatives required for classical models such as MMG. However, each method serves a different purpose, ranging from controlled hydrodynamic force measurements to realistic vessel trajectory validation and extensive parametric studies, and each comes with its own advantages and limitations. Table 2.3 and Figure 2.5 summarizes the usability of each method within contemporary manoeuvring research.

Method	Typical use	Strengths	Limitations
Captive tests (PM-M/CMT/OTT)	Controlled force–moment measurements; CFD benchmarking	High accuracy; physically interpretable; standardised procedures	Expensive facilities; scale effects; limited manoeuvre types
Free-running trials	Validating full-system manoeuvring (turning, zig-zag, etc.)	Realistic dynamics; captures full hull–propeller–rudder interaction	Weather-dependent; costly; reproducibility and sensor-noise issues
CFD (virtual captive)	Simulating PM-M/CMT motions; broad parametric studies	No scale effects; flexible scenario testing; detailed flow fields	Computationally costly; sensitive to configurations such as propulsor modelling, etc.

Table 2.3: Summary of conventional estimation methods for manoeuvring hydrodynamic derivatives. Representative works include Islam and Guedes Soares, 2018; Kim et al., 2015 (captive), Mitsuyuki et al., 2024; Okuda et al., 2022; Qiao et al., 2025 (free-running), and C. Chen et al., 2022; Dai and Li, 2019; Deng et al., 2025; Du et al., 2022; Lin et al., 2024; J.-h. Wang et al., 2019; Yu et al., 2024 (CFD).

Figure 2.5: Indicative trend from 2015–2025: steady growth of CFD/virtual-captive studies; PMM remains a benchmark; free-running persists as a validation anchor (C. Chen et al., 2022; Dai and Li, 2019; Deng et al., 2025; Islam and Guedes Soares, 2018; Lin et al., 2024; Mitsuyuki et al., 2024; Okuda et al., 2022; J.-h. Wang et al., 2019; Yu et al., 2024).

Recap. Conventional estimation methods remain essential for providing the hydrodynamic derivatives required by classical manoeuvring models. Captive tests and free-running trials offer reliable, physically accurate measurements but are costly, limited in manoeuvre type, and often difficult to reproduce. Hence, CFD has become

the best alternative, enabling virtual captive tests and extensive parametric studies, yet its outputs remain sensitive to numerical choices and solver configurations. These constraints collectively motivate the development of hybrid, physics-aware machine-learning approaches, such as the MARUS–PINN–LLM framework proposed in this thesis, which aim to preserve physical consistency while reducing cost, improving robustness, and enabling scalable, reproducible derivative estimation.

2.5 System Identification (SI): Estimating Derivatives from Data

System Identification (SI) provides a complementary path to estimating hydrodynamic derivatives, bridging the gap between classical model structures and the experimental/CFD-based methods used to populate them. While captive tests, free-running trials, and virtual CFD tests measure hydrodynamic forces directly, SI instead treats the vessel as a parameterised input–output system and estimates the unknown coefficients from observed manoeuvring trajectories. Although SI still requires data originating from experiments, sea trials, or CFD, it operates on motion-level signals (positions, velocities, yaw rate, rudder angle, etc.) rather than hydrodynamic force measurements (surge/sway forces, yaw moments, propeller and rudder loads, etc.), making it far less dependent on specialised tank facilities confined to laboratory conditions or full virtual CFD workflows. By minimising the mismatch between predicted and measured vessel responses to rudder, thruster/propeller, or environmental excitations such as the wind (Fossen, 2021; Ljung, 1999), SI preserves the classical model structure while offering a more flexible and data-driven way to parameter identification. In the maritime domain, SI methods are commonly grouped into three modes:

- (i) *Offline (batch) estimation*: performed on pre-collected trial data;
- (ii) *Online (recursive) estimation*: coefficients are updated adaptively as new data arrive;
- (iii) *Real-time SI*: directly embedded within the vessel’s Control, Navigation, and Guidance (CNG) loops to update parameters during operation.

2.5.1 Offline SI (batch/parametric)

Offline SI uses a fixed dataset collected from PMM/CMT, free-running, or high-fidelity CFD simulators and estimates a constant parameter vector for a chosen model structure (such as Abkowitz and MMG). Common SI estimators include prediction-error or maximum-likelihood methods, various least-squares formulations,

and Bayesian/MCMC¹ approaches that provide full uncertainty quantification (Ljung, 1999). Bayesian offline SI has gained more attention because it provides distributions for parameters and predicted trajectories instead of single point estimates.; for example, Mitsuyuki et al., 2024 use MCMC on free-running data to estimate MMG 3-DOF coefficients under uncertainty and generate trajectory predictions from the resulting parameter distributions. Having established these, the strength of offline SI lies in its statistical efficiency and reproducibility, however, its key limitations include: sensitivity to how informative the input data are, nonlinear or coupled models can be difficult to optimise, and performance may degrade when the operating conditions differ from the training data (Fossen, 2021; Ljung, 1999).

2.5.2 Online SI (adaptive/recursive)

Online SI continuously updates parameter estimates from incoming data using recursive methods, such as RLS² or dual EKF/UKF³.. This is useful for vessels whose hydrodynamic behavior varies with load, hull degradations, or sea conditions. While adaptive loops support better tracking performance in modern autopilots (Fossen, 2021), they are highly sensitive to sensor noise and require regular excitation to avoid parameter drift. Compared with offline SI, online methods adapt faster and reduce retuning time, but they face parameter identifiability issues (collinearity under limited maneuvers), sensor noise, and stability when disturbances change over time at sea (Fossen, 2021; Ljung, 1999). As an example of real-world online SI for ship dynamics, Zhu et al. (2017) demonstrate real-time RLS-based identification for maneuvering models using onboard data streams.

2.5.3 Real-time SI (streaming loop)

Real-time SI integrates the estimator into a GNC loop: *Sense* \rightarrow *Estimate states/parameters* \rightarrow *Predict* \rightarrow *Control* \rightarrow *Actuate*, with strict requirements on latency (fast updates), numerical stability (robust computations), and verification (ensuring reliable estimates). In practice, this requires fast computation (via using reduced models), robust estimators (regularized predictions), and real-time validation steps such as residual checks or parameter bounds to prevent the estimator from becoming unstable. The benefit is fast adaptation to dynamic marine conditions; and the drawback is sensitivity to poor sensor excitation and other anomalies. Recent work shows that Bayesian offline methods (Mitsuyuki et al., 2024) provide uncertainty

¹MCMC = Markov Chain Monte Carlo, a Bayesian sampling method that approximates the full probability distribution of model parameters by generating a chain of random samples.

²RLS = Recursive Least Squares, an adaptive algorithm that updates parameter estimates in real time by minimizing prediction errors as new measurements arrive.

³EKF = Extended Kalman Filter, UKF = Unscented Kalman Filter

estimates that help inform real-time applications, too. These three modes of system identification and their chronological evolution in the marine domain are illustrated in Fig. 2.6.

Figure 2.6: System identification modes and their chronological development: (i) *offline/batch* estimation from pre-collected datasets (dominant pre-2015); (ii) *online/recursive* adaptation with streaming measurements (2015–2020); (iii) *real-time* SI embedded in guidance–navigation–control (GNC) loops (emerging post-2020). Representative estimators include MCMC Mitsuyuki et al., 2024, recursive least-squares (RLS), and Kalman filter variants Fossen, 2021; Zhu et al., 2017.

Critical Synthesis across SI Modes Taken together, *Offline* SI delivers statistically valid, reproducible estimates but struggles with transferability. *Online* SI adapts, on the other hand, is fragile without persistent excitation and robust filtering. *Real-time* SI enables autonomy but adds hard constraints on latency and verification. Across these approaches, three key challenges recur: (i) designing inputs to adequately excite coupled and nonlinear terms, (ii) collinearity and identifiability issues in Abkowitz/MMG parameterizations, and (iii) uncertainty quantification to support certification and controller tuning (Fossen, 2021; Ljung, 1999; Mitsuyuki et al., 2024). These recurring issues have driven recent shifts toward Bayesian estimation, grey-box learning, and safeguard runtime mechanisms, which are to be reviewed in the following section.

2.5.4 Recent Advances and How SI Fits In

Over the last decade, SI has matured into a complementary tool for experimental and CFD-based approaches. Offline SI captures full-scale behaviour from operational data, while online SI updates coefficients as operating conditions evolve, and real-time SI enables parameter adaptation directly within the control loop. The goal is not to replace PMM or CFD, but to reduce scale effects, adapt to changing sea conditions, and maintain consistency under nonlinear manoeuvring states (H. Xu and Guedes Soares, 2025).

Bayesian identification and uncertainty quantification. A defining shift over the last few years has been the widespread use of Bayesian inference for maneuvering models. Rather than reporting only single point estimates, extending parameter uncertainty into trajectory ranges has become the trend, making the level of confidence in predictions explicit. For example, Mitsuyuki et al. (2024) and Xue et al. (2020) show that reporting uncertainty ranges for parameter estimation influences both trajectory predictions (zigzag) and the determination of safe maneuvering boundaries. These results highlight a core issue: over-parameterized models (Abkowitz/MMG with cross-coupling) may seem to fit the data at first glance, but the posterior distributions reveal which derivatives the data fail to determine. This makes Bayesian SI valuable not so much for improving accuracy, but for flagging cases where the data–model system is non-identifiable.

Nonparametric and grey-box identification. Parallel to Bayesian approaches, nonparametric and grey-box pipelines have evolved to balance prediction accuracy with interpretability. Gaussian Process models optimized with evolutionary algorithms (optimization methods inspired by natural selection, such as genetic algorithms) have been shown to match or outperform MMG predictions, while also providing predictive uncertainty as part of the output (Ouyang and Zou, 2021). Grey-box methods keep the MMG-style decomposition of the ship’s overall maneuvering forces/moments but estimate only poorly known submodels, with machine learning regressors such as LS-SVMs (L. Chen et al., 2022; Chillce and El Moctar, 2023). These strategies help reduce bias from model misspecification (when the assumed equations don’t match real-world dynamics), but remain fragile: kernel and hyperparameter choices heavily influence results, and physically unconstrained regressors risk breaking away from conservation laws unless physics-based penalties are enforced. Thus, nonparametric and grey-box SI are most useful in areas where the underlying physics is complex or poorly understood, such as rudder–propeller interactions, however, they still require careful tuning to render credible estimates.

Adaptive and real-time estimation. Recent field studies show that online SI can track changes/drifts in a vessel’s hydrodynamic behavior, but remains sensitive to parameter excitation. Zhu et al. (2017) reports the sensitivity of recursive least squares (RLS) to initial values and improves convergence via SVM initialized RLS on noisy zig-zag simulations. S. Wang et al. (2022), on the other hand, demonstrates faster convergence and better accuracy for nonlinear Gaussian filters versus Extended Kalman Filters (EKF) in real-time Nomoto-model identification using simulated Mariner zig-zag data. On a similar note, Zhao et al. (2022) shows that low excitation weakens identifiability, which improves with PRBS inputs and bounded estimation. For autonomy, this means identification can’t be a passive background task; it must

be integrated with maneuver planning, input excitation, and real-time validation (Fossen, 2021). A consolidated view of representative SI studies is shown in Table 2.4.

Table 2.4: Illustrative SI studies: data, estimators, and key limitations.

Study	Data	Estimator	Limitation
Mitsuyuki et al. (2024)	Free-running	Bayesian MCMC	Large uncertainty on coupled terms; needs rich maneuvers.
Xue et al. (2020)	Trials	Bayesian (3-DOF)	Sensitive to priors; difficult optimization.
Ouyang and Zou (2021)	Sim+exp	GP (genetic-tuned)	Kernel choice critical; weak physical consistency.
L. Chen et al. (2022)	Trials	MMG + LS-SVM	Depends strongly on submodel setup.
Zhu et al. (2017)	Onboard FR	RLS (online)	Unstable with weak excitation; noise-sensitive.
S. Wang et al. (2022)	Sea trials	Nonlinear GF	Requires tuning; waves disturb measurements.

2.6 The Advent of Machine Learning in Hydrodynamic Modeling

As the previous sections have shown, classical manoeuvring models depend heavily on accurate hydrodynamic derivatives, while experimental/CFD-based estimation methods and SI techniques each suffer from limitations such as high cost, sensitivity to noise, and difficulties with nonlinear/coupled dynamics. Over the last decade, the increasing availability of high-fidelity maneuvering data has facilitated the applications of ML into the domain of ship hydrodynamics and maneuvering. Unlike traditional physics-based or system-identification methods, data-informed ML approaches possess the advantage of learning complex nonlinear relationships directly from data. While these models often outperform traditional SI techniques in terms of predictive accuracy and precision, this gain usually comes at the expense of physical interpretability, producing so-called black-box models that are generally unsuitable for safety-critical operations; and they often generalize poorly beyond their training domain (Ariza Ramirez et al., 2018; Xue et al., 2020).

2.6.1 Support Vector Machine Regression (SVR) Approaches

Support Vector Regression, a kernel-based regression method that maps inputs into a high-dimensional feature space to capture nonlinear relationships without overfitting, was one of the earliest ML methods used in hydrodynamic parameter estimation. Early studies showed that SVR outperformed polynomial regression for predicting manoeuvring forces (Luo et al., 2016; X.-g. Wang et al., 2015), with later studies enhancing performance through least-squares SVR (LS-SVR)⁴ with wavelet denoising for the KVLCC2 hull (Hu et al., 2021), weighted LS-SVR⁵ for noise-robust autopilots (Zhu et al., 2020), parameter truncation for shallow-water modelling (H. Xu and Soares, 2019), and Grey Wolf-optimised SVR⁶ for limited full-scale trials (X. Zhang et al., 2022). Overall, SVR can estimate complex hydrodynamic coefficients with good predictive accuracy and reliability from limited data, but it remains a black-box method with limited interpretability, lacks the uncertainty quantification provided by Gaussian Processes (Section 2.6.3), and is sensitive to kernel and other hyperparameter choices, which constraints its use for safety-critical cases.

2.6.2 Neural Networks and Deep Learning

Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) have been used for maneuvering prediction since Oskin et al. (2013) and Rajesh and Bhattacharyya (2008), who showed that shallow ANNs could predict steering dynamics when system equations were unavailable. Later work expanded to deep architectures: Woo et al. (2018) modeled full-scale 3-DOF USV dynamics, and Wakita et al. (2022) predicted low-speed docking forces more accurately than MMG. Recurrent architectures, including Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs)⁷ and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks,⁸ have shown strong performance for time-series manoeuvring data (Hao et al., 2022). Recent studies further improved results using attention-based mechanisms⁹, with Dong et al. (2024) and D. Liu et al. (2025) demonstrating improved generalizability of LSTMs with attention mechanisms. Despite their accuracy, neural networks remain the least interpretable ML methods. Their internal weights do not correspond to interpretable physical coefficients, limiting their suitability for safety-critical contexts. PINNs

⁴LS-SVR: least-squares SVR solves linear equations instead of a quadratic system, making training faster but more noise-sensitive.

⁵Weighted LS-SVR: assigns higher weights to cleaner samples to improve robustness under sensor noise.

⁶Grey Wolf-optimised SVR: uses the Grey Wolf Optimizer to tune SVR hyperparameters automatically.

⁷RNNs: Recurrent Neural Networks that process sequences by feeding outputs back into the model to capture temporal patterns.

⁸LSTMs: Long Short-Term Memory networks, a form of RNN designed to capture long-term temporal patterns in sequential data.

⁹Attention mechanisms: neural modules, such as those in Transformer models, that highlight the most relevant parts of the input so the network can model long-range relationships more effectively.

(Section 2.6.4) attempt to address this gap by embedding physical constraints directly into the training objective of the neural network.

2.6.3 Gaussian Process and Bayesian Methods

Gaussian Process (GP) regression stands out among ML methods because it provides both predictions and full probabilistic uncertainty estimates, a key requirement in safety-critical tasks such as autonomous collision avoidance. Multi-output GPs¹⁰ have outperformed RNNs while offering confidence scores for 4-DOF hydrodynamic states (Ariza Ramirez et al., 2018); noisy-input GP models improve robustness to measurement noise on zigzag and turning-circle manoeuvres (Xue et al., 2020); and sparse, similarity-based GP¹¹ variants achieve high accuracy with far less data, as shown for the KVLCC2 hull (G. Chen et al., 2021). Compared with SVR, GPs are more data-efficient and more interpretable due to their uncertainty quantification, but their high computational cost limits their use to offline identification rather than real-time digital-twin applications.

2.6.4 Hybrid Grey-Box Models and Physics-Informed Learning

In terms of addressing the accuracy–interpretability trade-off, hybrid grey- arguably represent the most promising future direction in hydrodynamic research. These models combine the adaptability of machine learning with classical physical frameworks, such as the MMG model, preserving interpretability while enhancing data-driven flexibility. Suyama et al. (2024) fine-tuned MMG parameters directly on real-scale operational time-series data under physically plausible constraints, improving trajectory-level prediction accuracy. Whereas, Papandreou et al. (2025) predicted interpretable data-informed parameters, improving accuracy by 52–58% and consistency by 72–90% across two container ships while maintaining physical realism. Similarly, Mei et al. (2019) combined a physics reference model with Random Forest residual learning (a white–black-box hybrid model), achieving effective identification with limited availability of free-running data.

¹⁰Multi-output GPs: Gaussian Process models that predict several related signals such as surge, sway, and yaw at once, capturing how these outputs influence each other rather than modelling them separately.

¹¹Sparse GP: a computationally efficient form of a full Gaussian Process that uses a small set of data, reducing complexity. Similarity-based GP: a GP variant that uses a kernel shaped around how similar different manoeuvres or vessel states are, helping the model learn more efficiently and behave more robustly in hydrodynamic settings.

Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs) go further by embedding governing equations, typically partial differential equations (PDEs), directly into the training objective, enforcing physical consistency alongside data fitting. The loss function penalizes both empirical error and violations of physical laws, such as momentum balance. Alam et al. (2025) showed that PINNs predicted vessel trajectories 32% more accurately across deep learning baselines (including LSTMs and Transformers), while enforcing physical consistency through kinematic constraints such as smooth accelerations and realistic turn rates.

Hybrid and physics-informed approaches mark a clear shift toward interpretable, autonomy-ready hydrodynamic modeling. Unlike pure black-box methods, they reduce extreme data demands and improve generalization/extrapolation to unseen maneuvering scenarios. However, they still face difficulties in achieving stable convergence during training and accurately representing complex fluid dynamics such as turbulence, but they offer the most promising path forward.

Table 2.5: Comparative assessment of ML methods for ship hydrodynamic modeling (2013–2025), summarized from representative studies (Alamouh and Ölçer, 2025; Hu et al., 2021; D. Liu et al., 2025; Y. Liu et al., 2018; Papandreou et al., 2025; H. Xu and Soares, 2019; X. Zhang et al., 2022; Zhu et al., 2020).

Method	Data needs	Interpretability	Uncertainty	Extrapolation	Comp. cost
SVR	Low–Moderate	Low	✗	Moderate	Moderate
ANN / Deep NN	High	Very Low	✗	Poor	High
Gaussian Process (GP)	Low	Moderate	✓	Moderate	Very High
Hybrid Grey-box	Moderate	High	Partial	Good	Moderate
PINNs	Moderate	High	✓ (via constraints)	Good	High

2.6.5 Concluding Perspective

Several key insights can be drawn from this section:

- **Black-box ML (ANNs, RNNs):** High predictive power but poor interpretability and reliability; risky for safety-critical vessel autonomy.
- **SVR/GP:** More data-efficient and moderately interpretable, though GP scalability and SVR hyperparameter sensitivity limit wider adoption.
- **Hybrid/PINN:** the best compromise between accuracy, physical consistency, and generalisation, aligned with future digital-twin and autonomy needs.
- **Historical trajectory:** Early 2010s work focused on SVR for nonlinear forces (Luo et al., 2016; X.-g. Wang et al., 2015); 2015–2022 saw rapid growth of ANN and deep-learning models (Wakita et al., 2022; Woo et al., 2018); probabilistic GP methods then emphasised uncertainty quantification (Ariza Ramirez et al., 2018; Xue et al., 2020); and since 2020, hybrid grey-box and physics-informed

approaches (such as Random Forest residuals and PINNs) have gained attention for combining accuracy with interpretability (Alam et al., 2025; Mei et al., 2019; Papandreou et al., 2025). Table 2.6 summarizes the most recent undertakings of hybrid modeling in hydrodynamic literature.

Table 2.6: Recent ML-based approaches for ship maneuvering and trajectory prediction (2024–2025) based solely on the attached papers.

Study	Task	Model	Data Source	Uncertainty Q.
Dong et al. (2024)	Manoeuvring motion prediction	Attention network with positional encoding	Full-scale sea trials (turning tests)	No
D. Liu et al. (2025)	USV motion and trajectory prediction	LSTM + Multi-Head Attention hybrid deep network	MMG/CFD-generated simulations	No
X. Chen et al. (2025)	Ship trajectory prediction	Crossformer (hierarchical transformer)	Public trajectory datasets	No
Papandreou et al. (2025)	Grey-box manoeuvring model identification	Physics-informed 3-DOF model + cNLSa	Two container ships (free-running trials)	No

cNLS: Constrained Nonlinear Least Squares, an optimisation method that fits model parameters while enforcing physical constraints such as non-negative damping.

2.6.6 Symbolic Discovery and LLM Guidance for Residual Physics

Symbolic Regression for Interpretable Residual Physics

Although PINNs integrate physical constraints into their learning procedures, their residual outputs can still behave like black-box corrections, which makes it difficult to understand what additional physics, or physical rules, the network is actually learning, which reflects the broader interpretability limitations of NNs discussed by Fan et al. (2021). Thereby, Symbolic Regression (SR), which searches for analytical equations that best describe a dataset, emerges a possible route to improve NN transparency by expressing learned behaviours as sparse and human-readable formulas. For instance, Champion et al. (2019) showed SR’s capability of highlighting the dominant physical structures in a system by recovering sparse governing equations from data. In context of fluid dynamics, SR-based methods have also been used to produce explicit

RANS closure terms Z. Chen and Deng (2024). While not specific to hydrodynamic modelling, such studies demonstrate that SR can convert complicated NN-extracted residual patterns into human-readable expressions, which is highly relevant and useful for interpreting unmodelled force components in grey-box manoeuvring models.

LLM-Guided Equation Discovery

Even though SR-enhanced PINNs are more interpretable than black-box neural networks, classical SR techniques still suffer from slow and unstable search procedures, especially when the search space of possible equations becomes large, which is typical of hydrodynamics. More recent work attempts to address this problem by incorporating Large Language Models (LLMs) into the symbolic discovery process. The LLM-SR framework Shojaee et al. (2025) uses an LLM to propose equation structures that are scientifically plausible and syntactically valid before optimization, which helps reduce the otherwise dense search space. On a similar note, LLM-Feynman Song et al. (2025) uses LLM reasoning capabilities to impose dimensional consistency to the search procedure and guide the exploration of candidate formulas. Although both studies show clear improvements over traditional SR, they also highlight that LLM guidance does not remove the need for extensive numerical validation; the LLM simply narrows the symbolic search, it does neither replace it nor guarantee correctness on its own.

Overall, the combination of SR and LLM-guided symbolic discovery provides a promising, though still developing, path for turning PINN residuals into physically interpretable and meaningful expressions. For grey-box hydrodynamic modelling, this is particularly valuable, since understanding the nature of residual terms is just as important as predicting them accurately. However, the literature also shows that such methods still require careful validation and are not yet a complete solution to the NN interpretability problem.

2.7 Digital Twins for Surface-Ship Maneuvering and Derivative Identification

Reliable maneuvering prediction for USVs essentially depends on iteratively updated hydrodynamic derivatives. SI and ML methods can reliably provide these updates when coupled with physics-based models, but they require an operational structure that manages data streams, performs data-rich maneuvers, executes derivative estimation with confidence scores in real-time, and integrates the identified coefficients within control systems. Digital twins (DTs) provide this capability:

cyber–physical systems that fuse vessel data, models, and algorithms into a continuously learning digital representation of the ship (Menges and Rasheed, 2024; Menges et al., 2024).

In the maritime domain, DTs represent a paradigm shift from static simulators to dynamic, bidirectional replicas that still manage to render accurate predictions as vessels and their environments evolve (Markopoulos et al., 2024). For surface ships, an effective DT must not only mirror vessel kinematics but also update key hydrodynamic parameters, such as added mass, damping, and hull–propeller–rudder interactions, as they undergo gradual deviation under the effects of wear, degradation, or different sea states (Berg et al., 2025). Embedding online SI and ML within the DT enables such online updates in real time, reducing the gap between the modelled DT and reality (Menges and Rasheed, 2024; Menges et al., 2024).

Figure 2.7: Illustration of the digital twin loop for a USV. Observed vessel states are streamed from the physical platform to the digital twin for online parameter identification, while the twin generates model-informed trajectory and derivative feedback to improve prediction accuracy.

DT capability can be described through different maturity levels: Level 0 offers offline simulation only; Levels 1–2 add sensor integration and monitoring; Levels 3–4 predict and optimize vessel maneuvering; Level 5 closes the loop for autonomy by real-time model adaptation. These stages stage DTs as pathways to safe, efficient, autonomy-supportive operations (Kaklis et al., 2023; Markopoulos et al., 2024; Menges and Rasheed, 2024). Higher levels of DT maturity, however, rely on accurate hydrodynamic models (such as MMG) and online SI for continuous derivative updating (Markopoulos et al., 2024). Without uncertainty-aware estimation or data-rich maneuvers, model parameters drift and system accuracy/safety declines.

Figure 2.8 shows a representative DT architecture where online SI/ML modules continuously synchronize the twin with its physical counterpart.

Figure 2.8: Conceptual architecture of a ship maneuvering digital twin.

Hybrid DTs that combine physics-based models with residual ML layers confirm this need for embedded SI within the twin. Nielsen et al. (2022) show that residual ML layers can correct unmodeled hydrodynamics during realistic maneuvers, highlighting the limitations of relying on static physics alone. Surveys by Zocco et al. (2023) and Madusanka et al. (2023) note that most maritime DTs still lack bidirectional synchronization and real-time updating. Menges and Rasheed (2024) depict DT evolution for autonomous vessels but emphasize predictive and prescriptive control cannot be achieved without SI integrated into the twin. Thus, embedding SI is no longer optional; it is the critical element that transforms a descriptive digital twin into an adaptive, autonomy-capable one.

Recent studies show that real-time digital twins are becoming feasible. For example, Bayesian DMD¹² twins for online state prediction (Palma et al., 2024), UKF-based USV twins (Qu et al., 2025), and twins that update parameters in waves as conditions change (Lee et al., 2022). However, none standardize or operationalize real-time hydrodynamic derivative identification inside the twin loop; most DT stacks are still custom-built, with little transparency or reproducibility in the SI process, making

¹²DMD: Dynamic Mode Decomposition, a data-driven method that learns the key motion patterns in a system to predict how it will behave over time.

maneuvering accuracy fragile where trustworthy coefficients are critical (Ermakov et al., 2025; Menges and Rasheed, 2024).

Gap (Thesis Motivation). Across applications, two limitations persist: (1) current maritime DTs lack interoperable and open frameworks for real-time hydrodynamic parameter updating, and (2) most do not integrate physics-based simulators with online SI/ML in a transparent loop (data ingestion \rightarrow excitation \rightarrow parameter re-estimation with uncertainty quantification \rightarrow controlled model update). Current maritime DTs remain manually built, hard to validate, and rarely reproducible (Ermakov et al., 2025; Menges and Rasheed, 2024). This thesis aims to close this gap by developing an open, end-to-end MARUS-based framework for real-time data management, informative vessel excitation, and gray-box derivative estimation, moving marine DTs from descriptive twins toward credible, closed-loop autonomy.

2.8 Existing Simulation and Software Tools for Estimating Hydrodynamic Derivatives

In Section 2.7, we argued that operationally reliable digital twins for surface ships must embed online SI/ML to keep hydrodynamic derivatives updated. Simulation acts as the enabling layer for that loop: (i) design and verify persistently exciting manoeuvres offline (zigzag, turning circles, coupled 4-DOF motions); (ii) act as the plant in SIL/HIL to safely validate online identification before deployment (iii) stress-test coefficient updates against environmental disturbances and sensor faults; and (iv) provide versioned synthetic datasets to benchmark grey-box estimators and uncertainty quantification. This section, therefore, critically reviews simulators specifically on their usability for derivative estimation in surface ships.

Classification axes. To compare the different simulators in terms of how useful they are for hydrodynamic-derivative estimation, we group them along five practical dimensions: (A) **Hydrodynamic fidelity**: this covers how well the simulator captures the vessel’s physics, ranging from high-accuracy CFD solvers (such as RANS¹³) to simplified MMG manoeuvring models; (B) **Runtime**: whether the tool runs at HPC time scales or can operate in real time, including SIL¹⁴/HIL¹⁵ testing; (C) **Openness**: the degree to which the tool supports open frameworks and reproducible workflows; (D) **DT/SI readiness**: how easily the simulator connects

¹³RANS: Reynolds-Averaged Navier–Stokes, a CFD approach that models turbulence for realistic viscous flows.

¹⁴SIL: Software-in-the-Loop, where controllers run against a simulated plant.

¹⁵HIL: Hardware-in-the-Loop, where real hardware interacts with a simulator.

to DT or SI workflows through interfaces such as ROS¹⁶, FMI¹⁷, or gRPC¹⁸; (E) **Coupling breadth**: the degree of derivative coupling between simulation modules, from fully coupled CFD solvers to weaker potential-flow (Pot.¹⁹) formulations or BEM²⁰/WEC²¹ approaches. Table 2.7 summarises these axes across the main tools used for USV manoeuvring and derivative identification.

Table 2.7: Comparative assessment of major simulation platforms for USV hydrodynamic derivative estimation. Synthesized from: C. Chen et al., 2022; Fossen and Perez, 2004; Grimaldi et al., 2025; Islam and Guedes Soares, 2018; Loncar et al., 2022; Mucha et al., 2023; Potokar et al., 2022; Smith and Dunbabin, 2019; Wu et al., 2023; Yasukawa and Yoshimura, 2015.

Platform	Domain	Fidelity	Real-time	Speed Factor	DT/SI Ready	Coupling Type
ProteusDS	Marine dynamics	Med.	✗	0	Low (Offline/No live exchange)	Decoupled
STAR-CCM+	Multi-physics CFD	VH	✗	0	Low (File-based)	Fully coupled
CFDSHIP-Iowa	RANS CFD	VH	✗	0	Low (Offline only)	Fully coupled
OpenFOAM / naoe-FOAM	General CFD	VH	✗	0	Low-Med (Extensible; ML interfaces)	Fully coupled
ReFRESCO	RANS CFD	VH	✗	0	Low (Offline coefficients)	Fully coupled
SHIPFLOW	Hybrid (Pot. + RANS)	High	✗	0	Low (File-based)	Weakly coupled
WEC-Sim	WEC modelling	Med.	Partially	~ 1×	Med. (SIL/HIL capable)	Weakly coupled
Capitaine	BEM hydrodynamics	Med.	✗	0	Med. (Transparent data)	Weakly coupled
MSS/MANSIM	Maneuvering (MMG)	Med.	✓	1×	Low-Med (SIL/HIL; MATLAB)	Decoupled
Gazebo UUV / DAVE	Robotics simulation	M-L	✓	1-50×	High (ROS2-native)	Decoupled
ASVSim	Autonomy	M-L	✓	1-5×	High (ROS, HIL-ready)	Decoupled
Stonefish	Robotics + sensors	M-L	✓	1-20×	High (ML datasets; ROS2/C++)	Decoupled
MARUS (Unity)	Multi-robot sim	M-L	✓	1-20×	High (ROS2/gRPC; multi-agent)	Decoupled
HoloOcean / UNav-Sim	Unreal-based sim	M-L	✓	1-50×	High (Photo-real; ROS2/Python)	Decoupled
OceanSim family	Sea-state modelling	Low	✓	1-10×	Med-High (Environment realism)	Decoupled

Fidelity Ratings: VH: Very High (RANS CFD); H: High (Hybrid); M: Medium (BEM, WEC); M-L: Medium-Low (MMG, Robotics).

From Table 2.7, it is clear that the simulators differ a lot in terms of fidelity, speed, and how easily they fit into DT or SI pipelines. High-end CFD tools provide excellent physics but are too slow for real-time applications, while robotics and game-engine simulators run quickly and integrate well with ROS2/gRPC but rely on simplified hydrodynamics. Since these trade-offs affect how appropriate/useful each tool is for estimating hydrodynamic derivatives, the next subsections explore each simulator group more closely through a critical perspective.

¹⁶ROS: Robot Operating System, a middleware for real-time distributed robotics systems.

¹⁷FMI: Functional Mock-up Interface, a standard for exchanging and cosimulating models across different software tools.

¹⁸gRPC: A high-performance standard for structured and low-latency data exchange.

¹⁹Pot.: Potential-flow theory, an irrotational flow model used for fast hydrodynamic approximations.

²⁰BEM: Boundary Element Method, a fast hydrodynamic solver based on potential flow.

²¹WEC: Wave Energy Converter models using radiation-diffraction theory.

2.8.1 Industry-standard hydrodynamic tools (high fidelity, offline)

Commercial and research-focused hydrodynamic solvers such as ProteusDS (Bivol et al., 2017, 2018; Jeffcoate et al., 2016; Ltd., 2015), STAR-CCM+ (C. Chen et al., 2022; Li et al., 2024; Mucha et al., 2023; Software, 2023; Wu et al., 2023), CFDShip-Iowa (Aram and Mucha, 2024; Bhushan et al., 2009; Carrica et al., 2013; J. Huang et al., 2012; of Iowa IIHR—Hydroscience Engineering, 2023), SHIPFLOW (AB, 2023; Larsson et al., 2014; Tezdogan et al., 2015), and ReFRESCO (Baltazar et al., 2013; Eça et al., 2016; MARIN, 2023; Pereira et al., 2017) provide some of the most accurate hydrodynamic forces and manoeuvring coefficients available today. These tools are able to accurately reproduce complex hull–propeller–rudder interactions and run virtual captive tests at a fidelity level comparable to towing-tank experiments (axis A), as demonstrated in several validation studies (C. Chen et al., 2022). However, their heavy, closed architectures limit DT/SI readiness (axes B/D) and rely on fully coupled, computationally intensive workflows (axis E). None provide low-latency data streams for real sensors or runtime updates of derivatives, keeping them unsuitable for closed-loop identification. The same applies to vessel-design-focused platforms such as SINTEF’s ShipX family (Ocean, 2012), which supports early-stage design and operability analysis rather than real-time data integration. Thus, while essential as high-fidelity ground-truth generators, this group of simulators cannot support online or closed-loop identification within a DT. Tools such as WEC-Sim (Dizon et al., 2024; Lawson et al., 2016; Ogden et al., 2022) or Capytaine (Ancellin and Dias, 2019) offer more transparency but remain mostly offline.

2.8.2 Open CFD and control-oriented tools (transparent but slow or limited)

Academic and open-source tools sit between full CFD solvers and robotics-focused simulators. OpenFOAM and its variants such as naoe-FOAM (Foundation, 2023; Islam and Guedes Soares, 2018; Maulik, Fytanidis, et al., 2021; Maulik, Sharma, et al., 2021; J.-h. Wang et al., 2019) provide transparent, fully customisable CFD environments that are widely used for virtual captive tests and hydrodynamic benchmarking. They have also been adapted for hybrid ML/CFD workflows, but even well-optimised RANS simulations remain far from real-time applicability and are therefore unsuitable for online SI. At the other side of the spectrum, MATLAB-based frameworks like MSS and MANSIM (Fossen and Perez, 2004; Perez et al., 2006; Sukas et al., 2019; Yasukawa and Yoshimura, 2015) offer fast and physically interpretable 3–6 DOF manoeuvring models that are useful for early hydrodynamic controller or estimator development. However, they lack modern middleware integration (such as

ROS2) and cannot update parameters during real-time execution. Collectively, these academic and open tools provide transparency and configurability (axes C/A) and often rely on fully coupled and dense frameworks (axis E), but most are either too slow (CFD) or not well connected (MATLAB-only) for online, reliable SI. They remain invaluable for offline baselines and grey-box structures, yet do not, by themselves, close the twin loop (Islam and Guedes Soares, 2018).

2.8.3 Robotics-oriented simulators (real time, SI-ready, but simplified hydrodynamics)

Robotics-oriented simulators form the most practical group for real-time DT and SI experiments. ROS-based environments such as Gazebo/UUVSim (Manhaes et al., 2016), DAVE (M. M. Zhang et al., 2022), MOOS-IvP (Benjamin, 2018; Benjamin et al., 2013; Newman, Benjamin, et al., 2024), and ASVSim (Lesy et al., 2025; Smith and Dunbabin, 2019) support real-time operation, sensor emulation, autonomy testing, and large-scale data generation, which makes them highly attractive for testing identification pipelines in closed-loop scenarios. Unity/Unreal platforms, including MARUS (Loncar et al., 2022), Stonefish (Grimaldi et al., 2025), HoloOcean (Potokar et al., 2022), and UNav-Sim (Amer et al., 2023), push this further by offering photorealistic graphics rendering, advanced sonar and camera models, and native ROS2/gRPC communication. These features make them strong candidates for integration into DT workflows. Their main drawback is hydrodynamic fidelity: they rely on simplified models for forces such as drag, buoyancy, and added mass instead of detailed CFD. Even so, they currently provide the most practical environment for embedding online SI, grey-box PINNs, and data-driven correction models directly into a DT architecture.

Mini-timeline. Early 2010s tools such as MSS established MATLAB-based foundations for ship dynamics and control design (Fossen and Perez, 2004; Perez et al., 2006). From 2016 to 2019, Gazebo/UUVSim and ASVSim introduced ROS integration and real-time HIL testing for marine autonomy (Manhaes et al., 2016; Smith and Dunbabin, 2019). By 2019, Stonefish expanded this landscape with realistic sensor models and ML dataset generation. Between 2022 and 2023, Unity and Unreal-based platforms such as MARUS, HoloOcean, and UNav-Sim formalized multi-robot marine simulation with ROS2/gRPC connectivity, more photorealistic rendering, and sonar modeling (Amer et al., 2023; Loncar et al., 2022; Potokar et al., 2022). Most recently, benchmarking and acceleration frameworks such as URoBench and MarineGym have pushed faster-than-real-time simulation episodes and standardized evaluation for RL, representing a shift toward large-scale autonomy benchmarking (Chu et al., 2025; Z. Huang et al., 2024).

Figure 2.9: Timeline of surface-ship simulators vs. fidelity/runtime. MATLAB toolchains → ROS-native robotics simulators → Unity/Unreal stacks for autonomy. CFD solvers remain offline ground-truth providers.

2.8.4 Simulation Middleware and Data Interchange

Real-time DT/SI systems depend heavily on middleware that supports data streaming, model exchange, and parameter synchronisation across different nodes/modules of the pipeline. FMI enables co-simulation through Functional Mock-up Units (FMUs), but adoption in marine contexts is limited because of tooling gaps and inconsistent data models. The High Level Architecture (HLA) supports distributed simulation but is too complex for autonomy pipelines. ROS2/DDS²², gRPC, and MQTT²³ dominate practical implementations due to low-latency messaging, however, they lack native implementations for model coupling. These gaps motivate hybrid stacked models where ROS manages live data streams, gRPC supports efficient and structured data exchange, and simulators such as MARUS provide real-time execution with structured logging.

2.8.5 Summary

Across existing marine simulators, none provide both high-fidelity hydrodynamics and real-time autonomy integration. As illustrated in Table 2.8, CFD tools deliver highly accurate physics but remain offline and computationally expensive, while most Unity/Unreal-based simulators suffer from limited maintenance, insufficient marine-specific sensor support, or weak middleware connectivity. MARUS overcomes these limitations through validated marine dynamics, native ROS2/gRPC interfaces, and comprehensive marine sensor-actuator models, enabling efficient, data-streaming-appropriate, and closed-loop USV manoeuvring experiments such as the turning circle tests. For these reasons, and based on the decision criteria summarised in Table 2.8, MARUS was selected as the most appropriate hydrodynamic data generation platform for this thesis.

²²DDS: Data Distribution Service

²³MQTT: Message Queuing Telemetry Transport

Table 2.8: Decision matrix summarizing rationale for using MARUS over other frameworks.

Criterion	STAR-CCM+	OpenFOAM	Gazebo	MARUS	Justification
Real-time performance	✗	✗	✓	✓✓	Unity engine allows >10× real-time
Open interfaces (ROS2/FMI)	✗	✓	✓	✓✓	Native ROS2 + gRPC integration
Physics fidelity (SI base)	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓	✓✓	MMG + empirical models extensible
Data synchronization	✗	✗	Partial	✓✓✓	gRPC + structured logging layer
Extensibility / FAIR compliance	✗	✓	Partial	✓✓✓	Modular open-core architecture

2.9 Narrative Synthesis and Research Gap

2.9.1 Narrative Synthesis

The literature shows three disjointed fragments in manoeuvring hydrodynamics. Classical models (Nomoto, Abkowitz, MMG) provide physically interpretable structures but rely on costly and time-consuming experiments or computationally heavy CFD, which are not applicable to iterative learning or real-time digital twinning, for coefficient estimation. Therefore, modern data-driven approaches, including machine learning, grey-box models, and PINNs, improve real-time flexibility and accuracy but typically rely on offline datasets and offer limited physical interpretability.

Across these fragments, two major limitations emerge. First, existing simulators either provide realism without real-time capability (CFD) or real-time execution with simplified hydrodynamics (robotics simulators). Second, most hybrid or data-driven models act as black boxes, offering little insight into what their residual terms represent physically. No current framework connects real-time manoeuvre data generation, physics-informed data-driven learning, and interpretable residual discovery within a unified fully-functional pipeline.

2.9.2 Research Gap

The review highlights four specific gaps that remain unaddressed in hydrodynamic literature:

1. **Lack of reproducible manoeuvring datasets:** No open, real-time platform exists for generating synchronised, FAIR-compliant IMO-standard manoeuvre data suitable for hydrodynamic identification.
2. **Disconnected hybrid modelling:** MMG-based physics models and PINN-based learning exist independently, but no integrated MMG+PINN framework currently estimates coupled derivatives such as Y_r and N_v from simulated manoeuvres in real time.

3. **Missing interpretability tools:** PINN residuals are rarely examined, and no prior work uses symbolic regression or LLMs to translate data-driven corrections into physically meaningful expressions.
4. **Limited digital-twin readiness:** Existing workflows do not support a closed loop where simulation, identification, and model updating operate continuously at real-time speeds.

Thus, the gap is not a single missing method but the absence of an end-to-end workflow combining real-time simulation, hybrid physics–ML identification for physically accurate and meaningful estimation of hydrodynamic derivatives, and interpretable symbolic discovery via LLMs.

To address this, this dissertation proposes a unified **MARUS–PINN–LLM** pipeline that generates structured manoeuvring data in real time, performs hybrid MMG+PINN parameter estimation, and applies symbolic discovery to reveal physically consistent residual hydrodynamics.

2.9.3 Chapter Summary

This chapter reviewed classical manoeuvring models, experimental and CFD methods to populate those models, the system identification techniques developed to overcome the limitations of those methods, and recent data-driven and hybrid approaches that build on these models to improve flexibility and accuracy. While each contributes valuable capabilities, none provide a cohesive framework capable of real-time data generation, adaptive hybrid modelling, and interpretable residual physics.

CFD provides accuracy but is too slow; robotics simulators provide speed but lack hydrodynamic elaboration due to their simplified physics; and most hybrid models depend on static datasets and remain uninterpretable. These limitations motivate the development of the proposed MARUS-driven hybrid framework.

The MARUS–PINN–LLM pipeline overcomes these limitations by automating free-running manoeuvring-data generation, embedding physics-informed learning through a GreyBox PINN, and using LLM-guided symbolic discovery to translate residual terms into physically interpretable expressions. Together, these components form a reproducible as well as scalable basis for manoeuvring digital twins and next-generation maritime autonomy systems that require real-time, interpretable, and uncertainty-aware hydrodynamic model updates. The next chapter elaborates

on the methodology used to implement this framework, detailing the MARUS data-generation pipeline, the GreyBox PINN architecture, and the symbolic discovery process that completes the hybrid identification loop.

Chapter 3

Methodology & Presentation of Application

This chapter presents the complete methodology and practical implementation of the proposed MARUS-PINN-LLM framework, demonstrating how the proposed SI pipeline was realised in practice. It builds directly on the research gap identified in the previous chapter by translating the conceptual pipeline into a fully functional system. The chapter combines the theoretical design, manoeuvre data generation method, data conditioning pipeline, and hybrid modelling approach into a coherent SI workflow executed within the MARUS simulation environment. Section 3.1 details the MARUS scene configuration, vessel specification, actuation model, and the automated manoeuvre execution and logging system used to generate reproducible free-running datasets. Section 3.2 describes the complete data conditioning and preprocessing pipeline, including filtering, resampling, heading unwrapping, IMO/ITTC metric extraction, and identifiability analysis, resulting in a FAIR-compliant dataset suitable for hybrid learning. Section 3.3 outlines the implementation of the hybrid GreyP-INN-SR+LLM model, including the MMG-inspired physics core, neural residual network, symbolic-regression discovery, LLM-based interpretation, and fine-tuning procedures.

3.1 MARUS Setup

3.1.1 MARUS Scene & Vessel Specification

Simulator & project. All manoeuvres were executed in MARUS (powered by the Unity 2021.3 LTS engine) using the `ExampleScene` (Fig. 3.1) in the publicly available `marus-example` project. This scene contains: (a) a surface vessel whose physics root object is named `marus_boat`; (b) a visual child object `marus_boat_model`

containing the mesh `marus_boat_mesh`; and (c) the standard MARUS environment prefabs (ambient water sample, sky/fog volume, terrain). The simulation control operates within Unity's fixed-step physics loop. All input and output operations, such as reading vessel states and issuing control commands, are performed in the "FixedUpdate" function to ensure consistent timing across all simulation runs. The Unity fixed time step is the default "fixedDeltaTime" = 0.02s (50Hz); logs are then downsampled to 2Hz (accompanied by a 1Hz copy for normalization purposes).

Figure 3.1: Overview of the MARUS ExampleScene in Unity, showing the surface vessel (`marus_boat`) within the default maritime environment used for all manoeuvre simulations.

Coordinate & sign conventions. The Unity coordinate system is used throughout the data generation process: the $+Z$ axis points forward (surge u), $+X$ points to starboard (sway v), and $+Y$ points upward (Fig. 3.2). In Unity, yaw (heading) increases counter-clockwise (CCW), meaning that a starboard (clockwise) turn results in a decrease in yaw angle. The maneuver scripts controlling vessel behavior during simulation runs account for this behavior explicitly. For example, `ZigZagManeuver` uses `relSigned = -targetSign * rel` to ensure that the obtained zig-zag (ZZ) metrics follow standard maritime sign conventions (Algorithm 1).

Algorithm 1 Yaw Sign Correction

- 1: Compute relative heading: $rel \leftarrow \psi - \psi_0$
 - 2: Apply sign correction: $relSigned \leftarrow -targetSign \times rel$
 - 3: // ensures starboard turn is treated as positive
-

Figure 3.2: Unity coordinate system used for the MARUS vessel setup, showing the $+Z$ (surge), $+X$ (sway), and $+Y$ (heave) axes.

Vessel physics object. The root Game Object named "marus_boat" (Fig. 3.3) carries a Rigid Body with the following specifications: mass of 300 kg, drag coefficient of 0.5, angular drag of 4.0, and gravity enabled. The vessel's center of mass is intentionally shifted in `BoatPhysics` (approximately $Y = 0.2$ m upward and $Z = 1.0$ m forward) to represent a realistic bow-heavy trim condition. A convex `MeshCollider` is attached to the render mesh for physics consistency but is not used for contact forces, since all simulations used for model training and validation are free-running manoeuvres. Hydrodynamic forces are enabled through `BoatPhysics/DebugPhysics` using default MARUS coefficients: pressure drag ($C_{PD1} = 1500$, $C_{PD2} = 1100$, $F_P = 0.4$) and suction drag ($C_{SD1} = 900$, $C_{SD2} = 900$). These parameters define the baseline viscous/resistance conditions under which the SI process operates. Finally, no rigid body constraints are applied; the vessel achieves realistic 3-DOF planar motion through applied forces rather than kinematic restrictions.

Figure 3.3: Unity *Inspector* view of the `marus_boat` GameObject showing the `Rigidbody`, `MeshCollider`, `BoatPhysics`, and `DebugPhysics` components.

Vessel Actuation and Thruster Model. The vessel is actuated by two stern thrusters arranged port and starboard and controlled via MARUS’s `ThrusterController`; no geometric rudder is present in the scene. The physical thrusters correspond to the child objects `thrusters/port` (index 0) and `thrusters/starboard` (index 1), while a bow thruster object is present in the prefabs but is not utilized by our system. Each stern thruster is modeled using the Blue Robotics T200 (V16) datasheet included with MARUS for force mapping, producing approximately 14.65 kgf forward and 11.65 kgf reverse at full command. Course changes are therefore achieved through differential thrust. A rudder-equivalent substitute, $\hat{\delta}$, is derived from the commanded thrust difference and recorded for learning and diagnostic purposes (Algorithm 2). The lateral center-to-center distance between the two thrusters, which is used to calculate the yaw-moment proxy, is 1.2 m, with each thruster positioned ± 0.6 m relative to the vessel’s centerline.

Algorithm 2 Computation of rudder-equivalent substitute $\hat{\delta}$ in MARUS

Input: Thruster commands ($left, right$), vessel parameters ($maxRudderDeg, thrusterSeparation, thrustToForce$)

Output: Rudder-equivalent proxy $\hat{\delta}$, differential and total thrust, yaw moment τ_z

- 1: $diff \leftarrow \text{clamp}(right - left, -1, +1)$ // Compute differential thrust
 - 2: $\hat{\delta} \leftarrow diff \times maxRudderDeg$ // Rudder-equivalent substitute
 - 3: $InputDiff \leftarrow right - left$
 - 4: $InputSum \leftarrow right + left$
 - 5: $\tau_z \leftarrow (right - left) \times (thrusterSeparation/2) \times thrustToForce$ // Yaw-moment proxy

 - 6: Log $\{\hat{\delta}, InputDiff, InputSum, \tau_z\}$ for manoeuvring analysis
 - 7: Update engine telemetry
-

Scene Sensors, Controllers, and Rendering. The MARUS scene includes a standard collection of sensors such as IMU, GNSS, cameras, LiDAR, and sonar; for the present work, only pose and velocity from Unity physics and IMU yaw/yaw-rate are used. All high-level or autopilot controllers are disabled, and actuation is handled directly by the respective manoeuvre scripts. An AUV ROS Controller and `RosConnection` object are present to enable MARUS–ROS communication via gRPC/Protobuf. For visual rendering, the Ambient Water Sample provided in the example project is used; no HDRP/Crest water is applied, and visual settings do not affect vessel physics (Fig. 3.4).

Figure 3.4: Hierarchy view of the MARUS `ExampleScene`, showing the main vessel object (`marus_boat`), its associated sensor suite, thrusters, environment prefabs used for all manoeuvre simulations, and the ROS connection.

Maneuver Automation and Data Logging

Rationale and Standards. To characterise the vessel’s manoeuvring behaviour in a controlled yet physically realistic manner, a carefully selected set of standard IMO and ITTC manoeuvres (Table 3.1) was implemented. Each manoeuvre was chosen not only for compliance but for its ability to excite the vessel’s fundamental dynamic modes—surge, sway, and yaw—required for estimating corresponding hydrodynamic derivatives. Turning-Circle and Zig-Zag tests produce near-equilibrium responses, informing MMG-type coefficients ($Y_v, N_r, N_\delta, Y_\delta, N_\delta$), while Acceleration/Deceleration sequences capture surge damping and thrust dynamics (X_u, X_{uu}). Broadband PRBS differential-thrust excitation complements these deterministic tests by introducing frequency-rich input signals that expose higher-order and cross-coupled effects, supporting identification of unmodelled interactions within a data-driven framework such as the proposed PINN approach. Collectively, these tests provide structured, high-quality time-series data sufficient for planar 3-DOF hydrodynamic derivative estimation while avoiding 6-DOF or environmental influences outside the modelling scope.

Table 3.1: Standard manoeuvres and primary hydrodynamic derivatives excited.

Maneuver	Primary Derivatives Excited
Turning Circle (TC)	Y_v, N_r, N_δ
Zig-Zag (ZZ 10/10°, 20/20°)	Y_δ, N_δ (control response)
Acceleration / Deceleration / Crash-Stop	X_u, X_{uu}
PRBS Rudder	Coupled derivatives via spectral response analysis

Deterministic Control and Logging Architecture. All manoeuvre tests were designed to run autonomously via custom-built C# scripts, including: 1. ZigZagManeuver 2. TurningCircleTest 3. PRBSRudderTest 3. AccelDecelTest. These scripts interface with the previously described MARUS ThrusterController via the ControlBus, a static signal bus shared by all manoeuvre and logging scripts. The ControlBus ensures synchronized access to actuation and telemetry data (e.g., lastInputDiff, lastTauZ, lastRudderDeg, lastTorqueNm), minimizes runtime allocations, and guarantees that every logged data point precisely reflects the command applied to the vessel at each fixed-step physics update in MARUS. Telemetry from the virtual sensors and proxies ($\hat{\delta}$, τ_z , RPM, torque, input sum/diff) are continuously published, providing an identical signal surface for manoeuvre scripts and the BoatDataLogger (Fig. 3.5), which samples all relevant variables and writes them to synchronized CSV files at the 2 Hz rate (Algorithm 3). An optional 1 Hz copy ensures compliance testing, while each manoeuvre script implements its own continuous heading unwrapping routine (Fig. 3.6) to prevent $359 \rightarrow 0$ discontinuities during

long turns. The full set of variables logged by the `BoatDataLogger`, grouped by their physical and modeling roles, is summarized in Table 3.2.

Figure 3.5: Unity Inspector view of the `BoatDataLogger` component.

Table 3.2: Recorded data columns and their role in PINN-based 3-DOF hydrodynamic modeling.

Category	Variable / Symbol	Description (Units)	Role in PINN Model
Kinematics	<code>time, x, y</code>	Global time and planar position (s, m)	Time basis, trajectory reconstruction
	<code>heading_deg</code>	Unwrapped heading angle (°)	Orientation for body-frame transformation
Body-Fixed States	<code>u, v, r</code>	Surge, sway, yaw-rate (m/s, rad/s)	State variables in 3-DOF equations
Actuator Commands	<code>thrust_left, thrust_right</code>	Individual thruster inputs (0-1)	Direct control inputs / forcing sources
Derived Proxies	<code>input_diff, input_sum</code>	Differential and total thrust (-)	Reduced-order control representation
	<code>tau_z</code>	Yaw-moment proxy = $(T_R - T_L) \frac{L}{2} F_T$ (N · m)	Excitation term in yaw dynamics
Propulsion Telemetry	<code>rudder_deg_proxy</code>	Rudder-equivalent deflection (°)	Control effectiveness mapping (N_δ, Y_δ)
	<code>rpm, torque Nm</code>	Shaft speed and torque (rpm, N · m)	Energy-consistent surge dynamics and actuator modeling

Figure 3.6: Heading unwrapping in all manoeuvre scripts: (a) raw yaw angle wraps at 360° , (b) unwrapped heading accumulates smoothly for accurate $\Delta\psi$ computation.

Algorithm 3 Holistic Control–Logging Framework in MARUS

Input: Manoeuvre type $\in \{\text{TurningCircle}, \text{ZigZag}, \text{AccelDecel}, \text{PRBSRudder}\}$;
vessel parameters (d, F_T, δ_{\max})

Output: Time-adjusted control, telemetry, and data logging for hydrodynamic system identification

- 1: **Initialize:**
- 2: Reset `ControlBus`; set `isRunning` \leftarrow `true`
- 3: Engage `ThrusterController` and start `BoatDataLogger`
- 4: **if** the test defines an approach phase **then**
- 5: Perform steady approach ($t \approx \text{approachSeconds}$, typically 120 s)

- 6: **while** `ControlBus.isRunning` **do**
- 7: Read thruster commands (T_L, T_R) from the active manoeuvre script
- 8: Compute control proxies: [1] $input_diff \leftarrow T_R - T_L$ [1] $input_sum \leftarrow T_R + T_L$
[1] $\tau_z \leftarrow (T_R - T_L)(d/2)F_T$ [1] **Rudder proxy:** $\hat{\delta}[\text{deg}] \leftarrow \text{clamp}(T_R - T_L, -1, 1) \cdot \delta_{\max}$
- 9: Update engine telemetry ($rpm, torque$) via first-order lag and publish all values to `ControlBus`
- 10: Apply (T_L, T_R) to vessel via `ThrusterController`
- 11: **if** $t \geq nextLog$ **then**
- 12: Sample synchronized snapshot [1] $\{\text{time}, x, y, \text{heading_deg}, u, v, r, \text{thrust_left}, \text{thrust_right}, \text{input_diff},$
 $\text{input_sum}, \text{tau_z}, \text{rudder_deg_proxy}, rpm, torque_Nm\}$
- 13: Write row to main CSV log; $nextLog \leftarrow t + logInterval$
- 14: **if** `writeComplianceCopy` **and** $t \geq next1Hz$ **then**
- 15: Write the same to a secondary 1 Hz compliance log; $next1Hz \leftarrow t + 1$
- 16: // Automated Manoeuvre Logic:

- 17: **if** `TurningCircle` **then**
- 18: Maintain constant throttle; apply hard-over bias until $\Delta\psi \geq 540^\circ$
- 19: **else if** `ZigZag` **then**
- 20: Reverse control sign when unwrapped heading crosses $\pm commandAngleDeg$
- 21: **else if** `AccelDecel` **then**
- 22: Ramp throttle ($0 \rightarrow T_{\text{target}}$) or ($T_{\text{start}} \rightarrow 0$); optionally execute a reverse thrust for crash-stop
- 23: **else if** `PRBSRudder` **then**
- 24: Alternate $\hat{\delta} \in \{\pm\delta_{\max}\}$ by flipping sign every fixed `prbsInterval` (binary PRBS-style input)

- 25: **Finalize:**
- 26: Zero thrusters; set `isRunning` \leftarrow `false`
- 27: Flush/save all logs (`.csv`, optional 1 Hz copies)
- 28: Reset `ControlBus` to clear shared state

Automated Manoeuvre Scripts.

- **Turning-Circle Test (TurningCircleTest.cs):**

Implements the classical IMO/ITTC hard-over turning manoeuvre at a constant throttle. After a ≥ 120 s straight approach, the vessel applies maximum differential thrust to one side until the unwrapped heading change exceeds 540° , producing a coupled sway–yaw motion. The full set of parameters used in this test type is listed in Table 3.4. Each run automatically terminates when $\Delta\psi \geq 540^\circ$ or a 1200 s time cap is reached. The rudder-equivalent proxy $\hat{\delta}$ is computed linearly from differential thrust and bounded to $\pm 35^\circ$, while the yaw-moment proxy $\tau_z = (T_R - T_L)(d/2)F_T$ is logged at the same time as all the other kinematic states. A first-order lag model ($\tau_{\text{engine}} = 2$ s) simulates thruster RPM / torque dynamics for extra realism. Port and starboard runs are executed separately to identify steady-state yaw damping and control derivatives (Y_v, N_r, N_δ).

The following table summarizes all the conducted Turning-Circle tests:

Table 3.3: Turning-Circle Test Configurations and Corresponding Data Files.

Test	Turn Sign	Throttle	CSV File Acquired
TC at 0.6 – Starboard	+1	0.6	TC_S06_STBD.csv
TC at 0.6 – Port	-1	0.6	TC_S06_PORT.csv
TC at 1.0 – Starboard	+1	1.0	TC_S10_STBD.csv
TC at 1.0 – Port	-1	1.0	TC_S10_PORT.csv

Table 3.4: Turning-Circle Manoeuvre Configuration Parameters Used in MARUS Simulation

Parameter	Symbol / Variable	Value / Description
Steady approach time	approachSeconds	120 s (IMO standard pre-run)
Turn direction sign	turnSign	+1 = Starboard, -1 = Port
Hard-over bias	hardOverBias	0.95 (maximum rudder angle)
Throttle setting	throttle	0.0–1.0 (constant during turn)
Required heading change	requiredDeltaPsiDeg	$\geq 540^\circ$ (IMO/ITTC requirement)
Rudder-equivalent scale	maxRudderDeg	35°
Thruster lateral distance	thrusterSeparation	1.2 m (± 0.6 m from centerline)
Thrust-to-force coefficient	thrustToForce	100 N per unit command
Full-load RPM per thruster	rpmAtFull	1200 rpm
Full-load torque per thruster	torqueAtFull	800 N·m
Engine lag constant	engineTau	2.0 s (first-order response)
Maximum test duration	maxTestTime	1200 s (safety time cap)
Heading unwrapping	GetUnwrappedHeadingDeg()	$359^\circ \rightarrow 0^\circ$ correction

- **Zig-Zag Test (`ZigZagManeuver.cs`):** Executes the classical IMO 10/10° and 20/20° heading-triggered zig-zag manoeuvres. After a steady approach, the vessel performs repeated steering reversals when the unwrapped heading crosses $\pm\text{commandAngleDeg}$, with sign correction ensuring that starboard turns are treated as positive to maintain maritime convention. Constant throttle and symmetric thrust are maintained, while a predefined differential bias (± 0.95) emulates rudder turns. The test captures transient sway-yaw coupling and control sensitivity, producing high-quality temporal data for Y_δ and N_δ estimation. Similar to the TC test, a first-order lag model ($\tau_{\text{engine}} = 2$ s) governs thruster RPM and torque response. The full set of parameters used in this test is listed in Table 3.6.

The following table summarizes all the conducted Zig-Zag tests:

Table 3.5: Zig-Zag Test Configurations and Corresponding Data Files.

Test Type	Command Angle	Start Direction	Turn Sign	Throttle	CSV File Acquired
ZZ10	10°	Starboard-first	+1	0.6	ZZ10_S06_STBD.csv
ZZ10	10°	Port-first	-1	0.6	ZZ10_S06_PORT.csv
ZZ10	10°	Starboard-first	+1	0.8	ZZ10_S08_STBD.csv
ZZ10	10°	Port-first	-1	0.8	ZZ10_S08_PORT.csv
ZZ10	10°	Starboard-first	+1	1.0	ZZ10_S10_STBD.csv
ZZ10	10°	Port-first	-1	1.0	ZZ10_S10_PORT.csv
ZZ20	20°	Starboard-first	+1	0.6	ZZ20_S06_STBD.csv
ZZ20	20°	Port-first	-1	0.6	ZZ20_S06_PORT.csv
ZZ20	20°	Starboard-first	+1	0.8	ZZ20_S08_STBD.csv
ZZ20	20°	Port-first	-1	0.8	ZZ20_S08_PORT.csv
ZZ20	20°	Starboard-first	+1	1.0	ZZ20_S10_STBD.csv
ZZ20	20°	Port-first	-1	1.0	ZZ20_S10_PORT.csv

Table 3.6: Zig-Zag Manoeuvre Parameters Used in MARUS Simulation

Parameter	Symbol / Variable	Value / Description
Steady approach time	<code>approachSeconds</code>	120 s (IMO standard pre-run)
Commanded zig-zag angle	<code>commandAngleDeg</code>	10° / 20°
Heading deadband	<code>headingDeadband</code>	0.5° (prevents rapid reversals)
Initial turn direction	<code>startStarboard</code>	true (defines the first-leg thruster)
Throttle setting	<code>throttle</code>	0.0–1.0 (constant during test)
Rudder-equivalent scale	<code>maxRudderDeg</code>	35°
Maximum bias limit	<code>biasLimit</code>	0.95 (maximum rudder angle)
Test duration cap	<code>testDuration</code>	1200 s (safety time cap)
Thruster lateral distance	<code>thrusterSeparation</code>	1.2 m (± 0.6 m from centerline)
Thrust-to-force coefficient	<code>thrustToForce</code>	100 N per unit command
Full-load RPM per thruster	<code>rpmAtFull</code>	1200 rpm
Full-load torque per thruster	<code>torqueAtFull</code>	800 N·m
Engine lag constant	<code>engineTau</code>	2.0 s (first-order response)
Heading unwrapping	<code>GetUnwrappedHeadingDeg()</code>	359° \rightarrow 0° correction

- **Acceleration / Deceleration / Crash-Stop (AccelDecelTest.cs):** This manoeuvre isolates surge-axis hydrodynamic behaviour by configuring different throttle values symmetrically along the longitudinal axis. The script executes three standard modes: (*i*) forward acceleration ($0 \rightarrow T_{\text{target}}$), (*ii*) coasting deceleration ($T_{\text{start}} \rightarrow 0$), and (*iii*) crash-stop (rapid reversal into negative thrust). Each run produces synchronized time-series data of surge velocity, acceleration, and engine telemetry, supporting estimation of surge-related derivatives (X_u, X_{uu}) and thrust–resistance coupling. Similiar to other scripts, a first-order throttle ramp with fixed time constant ensures smooth excitation, while the `BoatDataLogger` writes commanded throttle, rudder proxy, and yaw-moment proxy (τ_z) to CSV for PINN-based identification. The full set of parameters used in this manoeuvre is listed in Table 3.8. The following table summarizes the conducted Accel/Decel/Stop tests and example file names:

Table 3.7: Acceleration/Deceleration/Crash-Stop Test Configuration and Data Files.

Test Mode	Throttle Transition	Description	CSV File Acquired
Accel	$0 \rightarrow 0.6$	Forward acceleration	ACCEL_S06.csv
Accel	$0 \rightarrow 0.8$	Forward acceleration	ACCEL_S08.csv
Accel	$0 \rightarrow 1.0$	Forward acceleration	ACCEL_S10.csv
Decel	$1.0 \rightarrow 0$	Coasting deceleration	DECEL_S06.csv
Decel	$1.0 \rightarrow 0$	Coasting deceleration	DECEL_S08.csv
Decel	$1.0 \rightarrow 0$	Coasting deceleration	DECEL_S10.csv
Stop	$1.0 \rightarrow -1.0$	Crash-stop into reverse	STOP_S06.csv
Stop	$1.0 \rightarrow -1.0$	Crash-stop into reverse	STOP_S08.csv
Stop	$1.0 \rightarrow -1.0$	Crash-stop into reverse	STOP_S10.csv

Table 3.8: Acceleration / Deceleration / Crash-Stop Manoeuvre Parameters Used in MARUS Simulation

Parameter	Symbol / Variable	Value / Description
Test mode	<code>testMode</code>	Accel, Decel, or Stop
Target throttle	<code>targetThrottle</code>	0.0–1.0 (target throttle for Accel)
Start throttle	<code>startThrottle</code>	1.0 (initial throttle for Decel/Stop)
Throttle ramp time	<code>rampSeconds</code>	20 s (linear ramp from start to target)
Hold time after ramp	<code>holdSeconds</code>	200 s (steady run following ramp)
Reverse-thrust enabled	<code>useReverseForStop</code>	<code>true</code> (applies reverse thrust for Stop)
Reverse throttle magnitude	<code>reverseThrottle</code>	–1.0 (full reverse thrust)
Straight-run bias	<code>straightBias</code>	0.0 (helps maintain straight course)
Maximum test duration	<code>maxTestTime</code>	1200 s (safety time cap)
Full-load RPM per thruster	<code>rpmAtFull</code>	1200 rpm
Full-load torque per thruster	<code>torqueAtFull</code>	800 N·m
Engine lag constant	<code>engineTau</code>	2.0 s (first-order response)
Yaw-moment proxy	<code>ControlBus.lastTauZ</code>	$(T_{\text{stbd}} - T_{\text{port}}) \times 0.6 \text{ m} \times 100 \text{ N}$
Heading unwrapping	<code>GetUnwrappedHeadingDeg()</code>	$359^\circ \rightarrow 0^\circ$ correction

- **PRBS Rudder Excitation (PRBSRudderTest.cs):** Implements a pseudo-random binary sequence (PRBS) as a broadband excitation signal applied to the rudder-equivalent differential thrust. After a short steady-state approach, the system alternates between $\pm\delta_{\max}$ at a fixed interval, generating rich frequency content that excites coupled surge–sway–yaw dynamics. This stochastic input complements the previous deterministic manoeuvres by revealing higher-order and cross-coupled hydrodynamic interactions otherwise unobservable in steady tests. Following the previous scripts, all telemetry, including commanded rudder proxy, thrust imbalance, and yaw moment (τ_z), is logged to CSV for subsequent PINN-based SI in this section as well (Table 3.10).

The following table summarizes all the conducted PRBS tests and example file names:

Table 3.9: PRBS Rudder Excitation Test Configurations and Corresponding Data Files.

Test Speed	PRBS Rate	Description	CSV File Acquired
0.6	Fast	Starboard-first PRBS	PRBS_S06_R_fast.csv
0.6	Slow	Starboard-first PRBS	PRBS_S06_R_slow.csv
0.8	Fast	Starboard-first PRBS	PRBS_S08_R_fast.csv
0.8	Slow	Starboard-first PRBS	PRBS_S08_R_slow.csv
1.0	Fast	Starboard-first PRBS	PRBS_S10_R_fast.csv
1.0	Slow	Starboard-first PRBS	PRBS_S10_R_slow.csv

Table 3.10: PRBS Rudder Excitation Parameters Used in MARUS Simulation

Parameter	Symbol / Variable	Value / Description
Steady approach time	<code>approachSeconds</code>	120 s (IMO-standard pre-run)
Test duration cap	<code>testDuration</code>	1200 s (safety time cap)
Throttle setting	<code>throttle</code>	0.8 (constant thrust during test)
Maximum rudder amplitude	<code>maxRudderDeg</code>	15° (PRBS switching limit)
PRBS switch interval	<code>prbsInterval</code>	5 s (time between state flips)
Thruster lateral distance	<code>thrusterSeparation</code>	1.2 m (± 0.6 m from centerline)
Thrust-to-force coefficient	<code>thrustToForce</code>	100 N per unit command
Full-load RPM per thruster	<code>rpmAtFull</code>	1200 rpm
Full-load torque per thruster	<code>torqueAtFull</code>	800 N·m
Engine lag constant	<code>engineTau</code>	2.0 s (first-order response)
Rudder-equivalent proxy	<code>ControlBus.lastRudderDeg</code>	$\pm 35^\circ \times \frac{\text{maxRudderDeg}}{35}$
Yaw-moment proxy	<code>ControlBus.lastTauZ</code>	$(T_{\text{stbd}} - T_{\text{port}}) \times 0.6 \text{ m} \times 100 \text{ N}$
Input proxies	<code>ControlBus.lastInputDiff/Sum</code>	Differential and total thrust

This unified execution and logging workflow, illustrated in 3.7 ensures that all variables required for classical MMG-model identification and data-driven residual learning in the hybrid MMG + PINN framework are directly observable from logged data without redundancy or dependence on derived quantities. The resulting synchronized CSV logs form the empirical foundation for the hybrid identification pipeline described in Section 3.2, where raw time series are resampled, filtered, and benchmarked against IMO metrics to ensure FAIR-compliant reproducibility.

Figure 3.7: Structured flow of the control-logging framework in MARUS.

3.2 Data Conditioning and Metric Extraction Pipeline

3.2.1 Data Conditioning

Subsequent to MARUS data generation, a comprehensive data preprocessing pipeline (Algorithm 4) was developed to convert raw simulator logs into physically consistent datasets suitable for hydrodynamic system identification. Each module in the pipeline addresses a distinct component of measurement or simulation bias (such as timing drift, noise, aliasing, or variable sampling), while ensuring numerical stability and cross-manoeuvre comparability through

uniform, denoised resampling, deriving standardized IMO/ITTC manoeuvring metrics (Turning Circle, Zig-Zag, PRBS, and surge tests) in a reproducible form, quantifying identifiability, dynamic coherence, and statistical uncertainty prior to PINN model fitting, and concluding with a first-order Nomoto model identification to provide linear benchmarks before exporting a task-appropriate, FAIR-compliant dataset for subsequent PINN training and validation.

Algorithm 4 Comprehensive Preprocessing and Metric Extraction Pipeline (MARUS Dataset)

Input: Raw MARUS CSVs $\mathcal{F} = \{f_i\}$; sampling rate $f_s = 2$ Hz; cutoff $f_c = 0.5$ Hz
Output: Clean, validated dataset \mathcal{D} with manoeuvre metrics, identifiability, uncertainty, and FAIR metadata

- 1: **function** PREPROCESSDATASET(\mathcal{F})
- 2: Init empty lists for processed frames, metrics, audits, metadata.
- 3: **for** each $f_i \in \mathcal{F}$ **do**
- 4: Load CSV; inspect stats and Δt stability.
- 5: Run timing audit (jitter, drift_{ppm}, missing rate).
- 6: Uniformly resample $\Delta t=1/f_s$; interpolate gaps.
- 7: Low-pass filter (u, v, r) via Butterworth($f_c, 3$); z-score clip outliers.
- 8: Unwrap heading; compute $r_{\text{heading}}=d\psi/dt$; store (u_f, v_f, r_f, δ, U).
- 0.3em // Outlier Cleaning and Yaw Alignment
- 9: **for** each D_i **do**
- 10: Apply rolling median+MAD filter; replace spikes.
- 11: Bandlimit and cross-correlate r_f vs. r_{heading} to find lag.
- 12: Shift, interpolate, and flag “ok/suspicious” via RMSE test.
- 0.3em // Manoeuvre Classification and Metrics
- 13: **for** each D_i **do**
- 14: Detect type $\in \{\text{TC}, \text{ZZ10}, \text{ZZ20}, \text{PRBS}, \text{ACCEL}, \text{DECEL}, \text{STOP}\}$.
- 15: **if** TC **then** Compute Advance, Transfer, Tactical Diam. ($/L_{PP}$).
- 16: **else if** ZZ **then** Derive 1st/2nd overshoots; detect reversals.
- 17: **else if** PRBS **then** Detect steps; compute PSD energy, peak freq, coherence $\gamma_{r\delta}^2(f)$.
- 18: **else if** ACCEL/DECEL/STOP **then** Derive time-to-90%, mean accel/decel, or stopping distance.
- 0.3em // Identifiability & Uncertainty
- 19: **for** each D_i **do**
- 20: Build $\Phi=[r, |r|, \delta]$; compute $\kappa(\Phi^T \Phi)$.
- 21: Compute $\rho_{r,\delta}$; flag if $\kappa < 10^8$ & $|\rho| > 0.5$.
- 22: Estimate $R=U/|r|$; bootstrap CI_{95%}.
- 0.3em // Surge Dynamics
- 23: **for** ACCEL, DECEL **do**
- 24: Fit $u=u_\infty(1 - e^{-t/\tau_a})$ or $u=u_0e^{-t/\tau_d}$; extract τ .
- 0.3em // Nomoto 1st-Order Model
- 25: **for** TC, ZZ, PRBS **do**
- 26: Fit $T\dot{r} + r = K\delta$ via ridge LSQ; save (K, T, σ_{res}).
- 0.3em // FAIR Output Assembly
- 27: Aggregate all runs $\rightarrow \mathcal{D}$; export `pinn_ready` train/val/test CSVs.
- 28: Generate dataset card PDF.
- 0.3em **return** FAIR-compliant data.

Signal Conditioning and Temporal Normalization. All recorded manoeuvre signals were first analyzed for temporal consistency by quantifying jitter, clock drift, and missing-sample rates. The raw time series were re-indexed onto a uniform 2 Hz grid and linearly interpolated to remove irregular sampling. A third-order Butterworth low-pass filter with a 0.5 Hz cutoff was then applied to the velocity and yaw-rate components (u, v, r) to eliminate high-frequency actuation noise. Remaining outliers were detected via $|z| > 4$ thresholding and replaced through a rolling median and MAD-based outlier-removal procedure, producing smooth and physically consistent trajectories (Algorithm 5).

Algorithm 5 Signal Conditioning and Temporal Normalization

Input: Raw MARUS log D , sampling rate f_s , cutoff f_c

Output: Filtered, uniformly sampled kinematic signals (u_f, v_f, r_f)

- 1: Load CSV \rightarrow DataFrame D
 - 2: Audit timing: compute jitter, drift_{ppm}, and missing rate
 - 3: Resample D to uniform $\Delta t = 1/f_s$ using linear interpolation
 - 4: Apply 3rd-order Butterworth low-pass filter to (u, v, r) with cutoff f_c
 - 5: Clip and impute outliers via z-score and rolling MAD window
 - 6: Compute filtered speed $U = \sqrt{u_f^2 + v_f^2}$
 - 7: Export (u_f, v_f, r_f, U) as conditioned signals
-

Yaw-rate alignment and consistency check. Measured yaw-rate r and heading-derived $\dot{\psi}$ signals were cross-correlated to estimate temporal lag τ and verify internal consistency:

$$\tau^* = \arg \max_{\tau} \text{corr}(r(t), \dot{\psi}(t + \tau)).$$

This stage was included to ensure dynamic synchronization between sensor-derived and computed measurements. Runs with root-mean-square error exceeding $1.2\sigma_r$ were flagged as “suspicious.”

3.2.2 Hydrodynamic Validation via Standard Manoeuvre Metrics

To validate the physical consistency of MARUS-generated manoeuvre data and its usability for subsequent PINN-based hydrodynamic identification, a set of standard IMO/ITTC metrics was computed for each test type. These metrics serve as benchmarks linking simulator fidelity to classical manoeuvring performance, supporting validation against real-world data and providing ground truth targets for the subsequent PINN-LLM modeling stage.

(a) Turning Circle (TC) Metrics. From heading-unwrapped trajectories, standard IMO-defined quantities were computed to characterize turning behaviour:

$$\text{Advance} = X(90^\circ), \quad \text{Transfer} = Y(90^\circ), \quad \text{Tactical Diameter} = Y(180^\circ).$$

These metrics (Figure 3.8) describe the vessel's turning response in terms of longitudinal progression (Advance), lateral offset (Transfer), and overall path trajectory (Tactical Diameter), normalized by the ship's length between perpendiculars (L_{PP}), serving as validity indicators for hydrodynamic fidelity in both port and starboard manoeuvres.

Figure 3.8: Turning Circle test geometry showing definitions of Advance, Transfer, and Tactical Diameter.

(b) Zig-Zag (ZZ) Metrics. Zig-Zag manoeuvres were also analyzed to assess course-keeping and rudder-response behavior. Overshoot angles were computed by detecting heading reversals beyond specified points, following IMO 10/10 and 20/20 standards. For each test, the following metrics were computed:

$$\text{1st Overshoot Angle } (\alpha_1), \quad \text{2nd Overshoot Angle } (\alpha_2), \quad \text{Execution Events (rudder reversals)}.$$

These metrics (Figure 3.9) capture yaw stability and rudder responsiveness. Symmetric port and starboard overshoots with high yaw correlation confirm correct control dynamics and consistent dynamic behaviour.

Figure 3.9: Zig-Zag (10/10) test figure showing definitions of first and second overshoot angles.

(c) PRBS (Frequency-Domain) Metrics. PRBS manoeuvres were also analyzed to quantify dynamic coupling between rudder input and yaw-rate response across a wide frequency range. Each sequence was segmented into binary step transitions, and frequency-domain quantities were derived from the filtered time series using Welch spectral estimation. For each test, the following metrics were computed:

$$N_{\text{steps}}, \quad \bar{T}_{\text{step}}, \quad |\bar{\delta}|, \quad f_{\text{peak}}, \quad E_{\text{PRBS}}, \quad \rho_{r,\delta}.$$

Here, N_{steps} is the number of detected input segments, \bar{T}_{step} and $|\bar{\delta}|$ represent mean step duration and amplitude, f_{peak} and E_{PRBS} are the dominant frequency and total spectral energy of the rudder input, and $\rho_{r,\delta}$ is the rudder–yaw correlation coefficient. These metrics describe how effectively the PRBS input excites the vessel’s yaw dynamics, supporting subsequent hydrodynamic parameter identifiability.

(d) Surge Acceleration, Deceleration, and Crash-Stop Metrics. Acceleration and braking manoeuvres were processed to evaluate the vessel’s surge-axis dynamic response and propulsion damping characteristics. Each run was analyzed to extract steady-state and transient-state behaviour parameters from filtered surge-velocity quantities. The following quantities were derived

for each test:

$$u_\infty, \quad t_{90\%}, \quad t_{10-90\%}, \quad \bar{a}, \quad \tau_a, \quad \tau_d, \quad S_{\text{stop}}.$$

Here, u_∞ means the steady-state speed, $t_{90\%}$ and $t_{10-90\%}$ represent rise or decay times to target velocities, \bar{a} is the mean acceleration or deceleration, τ_a and τ_d are time constants from first-order exponential fits to the speed response, and S_{stop} is the total stopping distance normalized by L_{PP} . These metrics validate MARUS surge-damping dynamics against expected first-order models.

3.2.3 Parameter Identifiability Diagnostics.

To ensure that the MARUS-recorded manoeuvre signals contained sufficient excitation for hydrodynamic parameter discovery, an identifiability check was also applied per run. The regression matrix

$$\Phi = [r, |r|r, \delta]$$

was assembled and its condition number $\kappa(\Phi^\top \Phi)$ computed. Runs with $\kappa < 10^8$ and $|\rho_{r,\delta}| > 0.5$ were classified as well-conditioned for derivative estimation, filtering out ill-conditioned datasets before PINN training and symbolic regression.

3.2.4 Nomoto Model Identification.

To obtain a linear benchmark for subsequent nonlinear PINN validation, each time-aligned manoeuvre dataset (Turning Circle, Zig-Zag, PRBS) was reduced to the classical first-order Nomoto model, which captures the dominant yaw dynamics between the rudder input δ and the yaw rate r :

$$T\dot{r} + r = K\delta.$$

The parameters K (rudder-to-yaw gain) and T (response time constant) were estimated via ridge-regularized least squares to reduce collinearity between r and δ :

$$\hat{\beta} = (X^\top X + \lambda I)^{-1} X^\top y, \quad X = [r, \delta], \quad y = \dot{r}, \quad \lambda = 10^{-3}.$$

The yaw-rate derivative \dot{r} was calculated by differencing consecutive samples using the resampled time step Δt . For each run, the identified parameters (K, T) were verified for physical plausibility ($T > 0$ and finite gain) and residual consistency through reconstructed yaw-rate trajectories $\hat{r}(t)$ from the fitted model.

3.2.5 Outputs and FAIR packaging.

All processed runs were aggregated into a single standard dataset containing filtered kinematic states (u_f, v_f, r_f) , rudder angles, and manoeuvre types. Additionally, FAIR metadata and a dataset card document the dataset version, source, and processing configuration for transparency purposes.

3.3 Physics-Informed Grey-Box Model for Maneuvering Dynamics

Building upon the processed MARUS dataset, this section describes the design, training, and validation of a hybrid physics-informed neural network developed to learn the maneuvering dynamics of the simulated vessel. The proposed architecture (Figure 3.10), termed **GreyPINN-SR+LLM**, combines an MMG-inspired physical core with a neural residual module, symbolic-regression-based discovery, and LLM-assisted physical interpretation.

Figure 3.10: Overview of the proposed hybrid GreyBox PINN workflow. MARUS data feed the physics-informed MMG core with a neural residual; symbolic regression and LLM interpretation extract and reinject interpretable hydrodynamic corrections.

3.3.1 Dataset Preparation and Acceleration Reconstruction

Following the completion of the preprocessing and metric extraction pipeline, the resulting FAIR-compliant dataset package served as the direct input for the GreyPINN-SR+LLM modeling phase. To avoid data leakage, each train, validation, and test split was organized by manoeuvre file (such as `TC_S08_PORT.csv`), preventing data leakage and ensuring that all samples from the same simulation run were contained within a single subset.

For each file, body-frame accelerations $(\dot{u}, \dot{v}, \dot{r})$ were reconstructed using a Rauch-Tung-Striebel (RTS) Kalman smoother implemented for each velocity

channel under a discrete-time constant-acceleration assumption:

$$v_{k+1} = v_k + a_k \Delta t, \quad a_{k+1} = a_k + w_k, \quad w_k \sim \mathcal{N}(0, q), \quad (3.1)$$

with process and measurement variances $q = 10^{-3}$, $r = 10^{-2}$, and sampling interval $\Delta t = 0.5$ s. This smoothing procedure rendered numerically stable as well as physically coherent acceleration labels, effectively eliminating residual telemetry noise that persisted even after the earlier preprocessing steps, as illustrated in Fig. 3.11.

Input features $[u_f, v_f, r_f, \delta_{\text{rad}}]$ (speeds, yaw rate, and rudder angle) were standardised using z-scores based on the training data to keep all variables on a similar scale, while target accelerations were kept in their original physical units (m/s^2).

Figure 3.11: RTS Kalman smoothing of the velocity components (u_f, v_f, r_f) .

3.3.2 MMG-Inspired Physical Core

To embed interpretable physical dynamics into the PINN, the physics core used a reduced 3-DOF MMG-type planar model (Algorithm 6):

$$M_{\text{eff}}\dot{\boldsymbol{\nu}} = \boldsymbol{\tau}_H + \boldsymbol{\tau}_P + \boldsymbol{\tau}_R - (C_{rb} + C_a)\boldsymbol{\nu},$$

where M_{eff} is the effective mass matrix integrating the rigid-body and added-mass terms, including the sway–yaw coupling $Y_{\dot{r}}$. The terms $\boldsymbol{\tau}_H$, $\boldsymbol{\tau}_P$, and $\boldsymbol{\tau}_R$ represent, respectively, the hydrodynamic hull forces, propeller-induced surge force, and rudder (differential-thrust proxy) contributions. The matrices C_{rb} and C_a include the rigid-body and added-mass Coriolis–centripetal components. Key coefficients were treated as trainable parameters but constrained to remain physically meaningful through differentiable activation functions (Table 3.11), ensuring, for example, that added-mass and rudder coefficients remain positive while damping terms remain negative.

Table 3.11: Physical parameter constraints applied to the MMG-based core.

Quantity	Sign Constraint	Physical Role
$m, I_z, X_{\dot{u}}, Y_{\dot{v}}, N_{\dot{r}}, Y_{\dot{r}}$	softplus() > 0	Added mass and inertia terms
X_u, Y_v, N_r	–softplus() < 0	Linear hydrodynamic damping
$X_{uu}, Y_{vv}, Y_{rr}, N_{vv}, N_{rr}$	–softplus() < 0	Quadratic (nonlinear) damping
a_Y, a_N	softplus() > 0	Rudder-induced sway force and yaw moment
t_R	$\sigma() \in (0, 1)$	Propeller–rudder blending coefficient
k_δ	restricted via tanh(·)	Rudder sensitivity
a_X	unconstrained (scaled by $(1 - t_R)U^2 \tanh(k_\delta \delta)$)	Rudder-induced surge correction

All modules were implemented to allow gradients to flow through the entire implementation, enabling the physics model and neural residuals to be trained simultaneously on an end-to-end basis.

Algorithm 6 MMG-Inspired Physical Core

- 1: **Class** MMGPhysicalCore
 - 2: Initialize trainable parameters:
 - 3: Rigid-body mass and inertia: m_{rb}, I_z
 - 4: Added-mass: $X_{\dot{u}}, Y_{\dot{v}}, N_{\dot{r}}, Y_{\dot{r}}$
 - 5: Linear damping: X_u, Y_v, N_r
 - 6: Quadratic damping: $X_{uu}, Y_{vv}, Y_{rr}, N_{vv}, N_{rr}$
 - 7: Cross-coupling: Y_r, N_v
 - 8: Rudder-related coefficients: $a_X, a_Y, a_N, t_R, k_\delta$
 - 9: Propeller/environmental: K_{T0}, K_{T1}
 - 10: **function** FORWARD(u, v, r, δ)
 - 11: Construct effective mass matrix M_{eff} with positive diagonals
 - 12: Form C_{rb} and C_a (Coriolis matrices)
 - 13: Compute hydrodynamic forces:
 - 14: Linear damping: $X_u u, Y_v v, N_r r$
 - 15: Nonlinear damping: $X_{uu} u|u|, Y_{vv} v|v|, Y_{rr} r|r|$, etc.
 - 16: Propeller force: $X_P = K_{T0} + K_{T1}|u|u$
 - 17: Rudder activation: $f_\delta = \tanh(k_\delta \delta)$
 - 18: Rudder scaling: $(1 - t_R)U^2$
 - 19: Rudder forces: X_R, Y_R, N_R via a_X, a_Y, a_N
 - 20: Assemble total forces:
$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = (X_H + X_P + X_R, Y_H + Y_R, N_H + N_R)$$
 - 21: Subtract Coriolis contributions: $\text{rhs} = \boldsymbol{\tau} - (C_{rb} + C_a)\boldsymbol{\nu}$
 - 22: Solve for accelerations:
$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\nu}} = M_{\text{eff}}^{-1} \text{rhs}$$
 - 23: **return** $\dot{\boldsymbol{\nu}}$
-

3.3.3 Grey-Box PINN Architecture

The complete model predicted the vessel accelerations as

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\nu}}_{\text{pred}} = f_{\text{MMG}}(\boldsymbol{\nu}, \delta; \boldsymbol{\theta}_{\text{phys}}) + f_{\text{res}}(\boldsymbol{\nu}, \delta; \boldsymbol{\theta}_{\text{NN}}),$$

where the residual term

$$f_{\text{res}}([\boldsymbol{\nu}, \delta]) = \text{MLP}_{128 \times 128}^{\tanh}([\boldsymbol{\nu}, \delta])$$

was designed to capture and approximate unmodelled couplings and nonlinear damping effects. Additionally, all model outputs were maintained in SI units

to preserve dimensional consistency.

3.3.4 Stage 1 – Physics Pre-Training and Stabilisation

The hybrid model (MMG-based physical core + MLP residual network) was first pre-trained for 80 epochs using a mean-squared-error (MSE) objective to initialise the residuals and align the trainable physical parameters with the measured vessel dynamics before introducing rollout-based stability terms:

$$\mathcal{L}_0 = \|\dot{\boldsymbol{v}}_{\text{pred}} - \dot{\boldsymbol{v}}\|^2.$$

Subsequently, a 50-epoch stabilisation phase added physics and rollout penalties to encourage temporal consistency and suppress drift:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{stage1}} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{MSE}} + \lambda_r \|\dot{r}_{\text{phys}} - \dot{r}\|^2 + \lambda_{\text{roll}} \text{Var}(r(t))_{\text{rollout}},$$

with $\lambda_r = 0.5$ and $\lambda_{\text{roll}} = 0.05$, with all fixed hyperparameters and numerical constants summarised in Table 3.12.

Table 3.12: Fixed hyperparameters and numerical constants used during Stage 1 pre-training and stabilisation.

Symbol / Parameter	Value	Role	Rationale
Δt	0.5 s	Sampling interval	2 Hz logging rate from MARUS dataset
λ_r	0.5	Yaw-rate consistency weight	Balances physics yaw term with data fidelity
λ_{roll}	0.05	Rollout stability weight	Tuned to suppress drift without over-penalisation
Rollout horizon H	10 steps	Rollout evaluation length	Captures short-term dynamic stability (5 s window)
Gradient clip norm	1.0	Gradient stabilisation	Prevents exploding gradients during backpropagation
ε	10^{-3}	Numerical floor	Avoids singularities in M_{eff}^{-1}
10^{-6} offsets	—	Positivity enforcement	Ensures parameters remain positive after <code>softplus</code>
Epochs (pretrain / stabilise)	80 / 50	Training schedule	Tuned for convergence without overfitting
Learning rate (pretrain / stabilise)	1×10^{-3} / 5×10^{-5}	Optimisation step size	Standard for AdamW; lower LR stabilises fine-tuning
Random seeds	[0, 1, 2]	Reproducibility	Multiple initialisations for robustness check

3.3.5 Stage 2 – Symbolic Discovery (PySR)

Following Stage 1 stabilisation, the residual accelerations $\boldsymbol{\epsilon} = \dot{\boldsymbol{v}}_{\text{data}} - \dot{\boldsymbol{v}}_{\text{phys}}$ were exported from the trained GreyBox PINN for symbolic regression. Each data channel (u , v , r) was fitted independently using PySR 0.16, which renders concise formulas that best reproduce the residual terms.

The symbolic search was restricted to a physically interpretable operator set,

$$O = \{+, -, \times, /, |\cdot|, \text{sign}\},$$

selected to capture common nonlinear and cross-coupled hydrodynamic effects while maintaining algebraic simplicity. For each output channel, PySR

generated a population of candidate equations that were ranked by

$$\text{score} = \text{loss} + 10^{-3} \times \text{complexity},$$

where the second term penalised excessive expression length and complexity. The best-performing symbolic formulas achieved validation errors between 10^{-2} and 10^{-1} rad/s² and revealed clear physical patterns; for instance, linear and coupled terms between surge and yaw (u, r) and nonlinear sway interactions, capturing dominant hydrodynamic effects with concise, interpretable structure. The discovered symbolic expressions, scaling parameters, and validation metrics were stored for the following stages.

3.3.6 Stage 3 – LLM-Based Symbolic Interpretation

To translate the symbolic residual expressions into hydrodynamically meaningful terms, each PySR-discovered equation was provided to a physics-aware Large Language Model (LLM) for structured interpretation. The model was supplied with (1) the symbolic expression in both its normalised and physical forms, (2) variable definitions and sign conventions, and (3) relevant operating context for the manoeuvring regime. The full prompt-engineering workflow used for this physics-aware interpretation is illustrated in Fig. 3.12.

The LLM did not modify the learning process or influence training; rather, it acted as a interpretability module. It returned a JSON-formatted description for each residual channel, including candidate hydrodynamic effects, concise natural-language explanations, and confidence scores. These structured outputs were later used in the Results chapter to support the physical interpretation of the learned model components.

Algorithm 7 Physics-aware LLM prompting for symbolic residual interpretation

Input: Normalized symbolic expression $f(\mathbf{x})$, scaling parameters (μ, σ) , vessel context

- 1: Convert to physical form $f_{\text{phys}}(u_f, v_f, r_f, \delta)$ using μ, σ
- 2: Construct structured prompt:
 - Role: "You are a naval hydrodynamics researcher"
 - Input: normalized + physical expression
 - Context: vessel type, speed, rudder limits
 - Task: identify MMG-style terms $(N'_r, N'_\delta, Y'_\delta)$
 - Output: JSON {effects, description, confidence, interpretation}
- 3: Query LLM (Gemini 2.5 Pro) \rightarrow receive raw JSON output
- 4: Parse effects \rightarrow store as `symbolic_interpretation_yaw.json`
- 5: Second-stage prompt: rewrite JSON summary in academic hydrodynamic language

Output: Final structured output:

Effects: {(name, description, c_i)},

Interpretation: Hydrodynamic paragraph (100–150 words)

Figure 3.12: Prompt-engineering workflow for physics-aware LLM interpretation of symbolic residuals.

3.3.7 Stage 4 – Symbolic Reinjection

The symbolic expressions obtained in Stage 3.3.5 and analysed in Stage 3.3.6 are converted into differentiable PyTorch modules and reintegrated into the GreyBoxPINN architecture. Each PySR-generated expression is transformed into a Torch-compiled function, rescaled using its channel-specific $(y_{\text{mean}}, y_{\text{std}})$ statistics, and clamped to ensure numerical stability during training. These symbolic residual terms are then incorporated into the MMG-based physical core through a bounded gain $k_{\text{sym}} = k_{\text{max}} \tanh(k_{\text{raw}})$ with $k_{\text{max}} = 0.5$, which restricts the magnitude of the injected corrections. The resulting physical acceleration is defined as

$$y^{\text{phys+sym}} = y^{\text{phys}} + [k_{\text{sym}}^{(u)} N_u, k_{\text{sym}}^{(v)} N_v, k_{\text{sym}}^{(r)} N_r],$$

after which an additional residual NN is applied to capture any remaining unmodelled dynamics. The overall reinjection workflow is illustrated in Fig. 3.13.

3.3.8 Stage 5 – Constrained Fine-Tuning

Stage 5 performs a constrained fine-tuning of the symbolic-augmented model. The MMG physical parameters, the new residual network, and the symbolic gains (after a 50 epoch warm-up) are jointly optimised using separate learning rates and a cosine learning-rate schedule. The objective function includes: (i) an MSE data-fit term, (ii) a physical-consistency term, (iii) L2 regularisation on the symbolic gains, (iv) a rollout-variance penalty to limit yaw drift, and (v) a rudder-sign constraint, $\max(0, \partial r / \partial \delta)$, which prevents non-physical negative yaw response to rudder input. The full set of hyperparameters used in this stage is reported in Table 3.13.

Figure 3.13: **Stages 4–5:** Symbolic expressions are reinjected into the physics core via adaptive gains k_{sym} , followed by fine-tuning under a multi-component loss enforcing physical consistency and rollout stability.

Table 3.13: Fine-tuning hyperparameters and symbolic-control settings used during Stages 4–5.

Parameter	Symbol / Value	Role	Rationale
Gradient clip norm	0.5	Stabilises optimisation	Prevents exploding gradients during long rollouts
Symbolic gain bound	$k_{\text{sym}} \in [-0.5, 0.5]$	Limits symbolic contribution	Ensures corrections remain physically plausible
Warm-up period	50 epochs	Freeze k_{sym} initially	Allows stable adaptation of the physical and residual components
Learning rates	5×10^{-6} (physics), 1×10^{-4} (residual/symbolic)	Per-parameter-group control	Slow updates for physical core; faster learning for residual and symbolic modules
Physics-consistency weight	$\lambda_{\text{phys}} = 0.1$	Encourages agreement with augmented physics	Balances physical fidelity with data-fit accuracy
Symbolic-gain regularisation	$\lambda_k = 10^{-4}$	L_2 penalty on k_{sym}	Suppresses over-amplification of symbolic corrections
Rollout-variance weight	$\lambda_{\text{roll}} = 0.1$	Stabilises long-horizon trajectories	Penalises excessive yaw drift
Rudder-moment sign penalty	$\lambda_{\delta} = 0.1$	Enforces $N_{\delta} < 0$	Prevents non-physical positive yaw response
Training epochs	500	Fine-tuning duration	Empirically sufficient for convergence
Scheduler	Cosine-annealed AdamW	Learning-rate decay	Smooth convergence with weight-decay control

3.4 Benchmarking and Evaluation

Three model variants (Table 3.14) were benchmarked under identical simulation and preprocessing conditions to quantify the effect of residual learning and symbolic reinjection. Each model used the same MMG-based physical architecture and shared normalization:

Table 3.14: Model variants used for benchmarking.

Model	Components	Purpose
PhysicsOnly	MMG core only	Baseline physical fidelity
GreyPINN	Physics + neural residual	Data-driven correction
PINN+Symbol	Physics + symbolic + residual	Full hybrid coupling

3.4.1 Evaluation protocol.

All models were evaluated across multiple random seeds using the held-out MARUS test set, encompassing standard manoeuvres (Turning Circle and Zig-Zag). Metrics comprised:

- per-file acceleration RMSEs for surge, sway, and yaw (u, v, r) ,
- 20-step rollout RMSEs for yaw rate $r(t)$ and heading $\psi(t)$,
- extracted hydrodynamic derivatives (Y_v, N_r, N_δ) at the mean operating point.

3.4.2 Hydrodynamic derivative consistency.

Linearised derivatives were estimated at the mean operating point from each trained model by automatic differentiation of the predicted accelerations with respect to v , r , and δ :

$$Y_v = \frac{\partial \dot{v}}{\partial v}, \quad N_r = \frac{\partial \dot{r}}{\partial r}, \quad N_\delta = \frac{\partial \dot{r}}{\partial \delta}. \quad (3.2)$$

3.4.3 Ablation Design (E1–E6)

A series of ablation studies (E1–E6) were conducted to examine the effect of specific modelling choices while keeping the data pipeline, optimisation settings, normalisation, and evaluation metrics fixed. **E1** establishes a baseline by comparing the three main models (**PhysicsOnly**, **GreyPINN**, **PINN+Symbol**) on held-out MARUS data. **E2** explores the role of rollout-consistency weighting by re-evaluating a stabilised GreyPINN under several nominal λ_{roll} values. **E3** investigates architectural sensitivity by testing wider and narrower residual networks (64 vs. 256) using untuned GreyPINN variants. **E4** examines label-generation effects by comparing validation performance using RTS-smoothed versus Savitzky–Golay-derived accelerations on the same trained model. **E5** performs an out-of-distribution check by applying all models to Zig-Zag files, noting that TC-only training is not repeated. Lastly, **E6** evaluates robustness by repeating all assessments across multiple random seeds. Together, these ablations highlight how the models respond to architectural, label, rollout, and distributional changes without changing the core training logic.

3.4.4 Statistical Evaluation Protocol

To determine whether the performance differences between models were statistically meaningful, a paired Wilcoxon signed-rank test was applied to ten matched test segments for each model. Multiple comparisons were controlled using the Holm–Bonferroni procedure. For every channel (u, v, r) and for the

mean RMSE, the median difference, the associated 95% confidence interval, the raw and adjusted p -values, and the corresponding effect sizes are reported (*d*).

3.4.5 External Cross-Speed Generalization Protocol

To evaluate the model’s ability to generalize beyond the training speeds (S1, S6, S8), a dedicated external dataset was incorporated into the evaluation protocol. This dataset consists of MARUS manoeuvres executed at an intermediate operating point (S7), including Turning Circle and Zig-Zag (ZZ15) tests to both port and starboard. The data were resampled, filtered, and processed using the same conditioning pipeline as the training datasets. Two complementary evaluation tasks were defined: (i) one-step-ahead acceleration prediction across the surge, sway, and yaw channels, and (ii) autonomous long-horizon rollouts of yaw-rate and heading under fixed rudder input sequences. This setup provides a strict test of cross-speed robustness and dynamic extrapolation, allowing the assessment of whether the learned model captures transferable hydrodynamic structure.

3.4.6 Discussion of Novelty.

The developed **GreyPINN–SR+LLM** framework establishes a closed-loop learning system in which:

1. The physics-informed core enforces interpretability and numerical stability.
2. The neural residual learns unmodelled nonlinear effects from data.
3. Symbolic regression and LLM feedback yield explainable hydrodynamic corrections.

This hybrid methodology advances data-driven ship-manoeuving research toward physically consistent and interpretable estimation of hydrodynamic derivatives. Its integration of PINN, symbolic discovery, and LLM interpretation represents a novel contribution to explainable maritime AI.

Chapter 4

Results and Data Analysis

This chapter presents the evaluation results of the end-to-end SI pipeline detailed in Chapter 3. The evaluation is structured in such a way to validate each stage of the framework individually as well as holistically, from the initial data conditioning and classical system identification to the final benchmarking and ablation studies of the proposed GreyPINN–SR+LLM model.

Section 4.1 concerns the quality as well as identifiability of MARUS-generated data by presenting the outcomes of the data conditioning pipeline, including the extracted IMO/ITTC metrics and the baseline first-order Nomoto model parameters. Section 4.2 depicts the results from each stage of the hybrid model’s development, including training behavior, the discovered symbolic expressions, and their physical interpretation by the LLM. Section 4.3 provides a comprehensive quantitative and qualitative comparison of the final PINN+Symbol model against the PhysicsOnly and GreyPINN baselines. Finally, Section 4.4 presents a strong collection of ablation studies to test the sensitivity and significance of the model’s key design components, followed by a generalizability test on unseen data.

4.1 Data Validation and Classical Benchmarks

To validate the physical consistency of MARUS-generated manoeuvre data and its usability for subsequent hydrodynamic identification, a set of standard IMO/ITTC metrics was computed for each test type. These metrics serve as ground-truth benchmarks against which the physical realism of the simulated data can be evaluated.

Yaw-Rate Consistency. Following the heading-unwrapping and yaw-alignment procedure defined in Section 3.2, the fidelity of the logged sensor data was first verified by comparing the measured yaw-rate (r_f) against the numerically-

derived yaw-rate ($\dot{\psi}$) computed from the unwrapped heading. After alignment via cross-correlation to estimate the temporal lag τ^* , the signals showed strong agreement, as shown in Figure 4.1. The Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) between the two signals was found to be consistently low, such as 0.002 rad/s for the TC S1.0 STBD run, and runs exceeding $1.2\sigma_r$ were flagged as "suspicious". This confirms the high internal consistency of the simulated data.

Figure 4.1: Yaw-rate alignment for a representative Turning Circle manoeuvre. The measured yaw-rate r_f (blue) and the heading-derived rate $\dot{\psi}$ (red dashed) show high correlation and minimal lag after alignment.

4.1.1 Standard Manoeuvre Metrics

Standard IMO/ITTC metrics, introduced in Section 3.2.2, were extracted from all processed manoeuvre files to validate that the MARUS simulator data against physically realistic vessel behaviour.

- **Turning Circle (TC):** Metrics including Advance, Transfer, and Tactical Diameter (Figure 3.8) were computed and non-dimensionalised by L_{PP} . The results, summarised in Table 4.1, show consistent turning behavior across 3 different speeds and 2 directions.

Table 4.1: Turning Circle (TC) metrics for port and starboard manoeuvres across three speed conditions.

File	Advance/ L_{PP}	Transfer/ L_{PP}	Tactical/ L_{PP}	Yaw Corr.	Yaw RMSE	Flag
TC_S1.0_PORT	93.9	10.1	8.3	0.999	0.002	ok
TC_S1.0_STBD	91.1	6.0	7.2	0.999	0.002	ok
TC_S06_PORT	88.2	30.0	28.2	0.999	0.003	ok
TC_S06_STBD	85.2	26.6	27.7	0.999	0.003	ok
TC_S08_PORT	90.4	20.0	18.2	0.999	0.003	ok
TC_S08_STBD	87.5	16.3	17.4	0.999	0.002	ok

- **Zig-Zag (ZZ):** First and second overshoot angles (α_1, α_2) for 10/10° and 20/20° tests (Figure 3.9) were extracted. The results in Table 4.2 show symmetric and stable overshoots, confirming correct control response dynamics.

Table 4.2: Zig-Zag (ZZ) overshoot metrics for 10/10 and 20/20 manoeuvres.

File	Cmd [°]	Events	1st OS [°]	2nd OS [°]	Yaw Corr.	Yaw RMSE	Flag
ZZ10_S1.0_PORT	10	4	8.9	9.3	0.999	0.001	ok
ZZ10_S1.0_STBD	10	4	8.8	9.0	0.998	0.001	ok
ZZ10_S06_PORT	10	4	8.1	9.0	0.998	0.002	ok
ZZ10_S06_STBD	10	4	8.4	9.0	0.998	0.002	ok
ZZ20_S1.0_PORT	20	4	17.6	19.7	0.999	0.002	ok
ZZ20_S1.0_STBD	20	4	18.0	19.6	0.999	0.002	ok
ZZ20_S08_PORT	20	4	17.0	18.7	0.999	0.004	ok
ZZ20_S08_STBD	20	4	17.3	18.5	0.999	0.004	ok

- **PRBS:** Frequency-domain analysis confirmed that the PRBS manoeuvres provided rich excitations. The Power Spectral Densities (PSD) and coherence plots (Figure 4.2) show significant power across the respective frequencies and high coherence ($\gamma_{r\delta}^2$) between rudder input and yaw-rate response. The corresponding quantitative data in Table 4.3 confirm that the PRBS inputs were repeatable and dynamically sufficient for exciting sway–yaw coupling.

Figure 4.2: Representative PRBS frequency-domain characterization, showing high coherence ($\gamma_{r\delta}^2$) between rudder and yaw-rate response in the relevant frequency band.

Table 4.3: PRBS manoeuvre characteristics across speeds.

File	Steps	Step Amp [°]	f_{peak} [Hz]	Energy	Yaw Corr.	Flag
PRBS_S1.0_R_fast	61	14.8	0.172	135.3	-0.76	ok
PRBS_S1.0_R_slow	31	14.5	0.078	135.4	-0.88	ok
PRBS_S08_R_fast	61	14.8	0.172	135.3	-0.75	ok
PRBS_S08_R_slow	31	14.5	0.078	135.4	-0.88	ok

- **Surge & Stop:** Acceleration, deceleration, and crash-stop metrics (Table 4.4) provided clear data on the vessel’s longitudinal dynamics, including time-to-90% ($t_{90\%}$) and stopping distances (S_{stop}). First-order exponential fits provided estimates for time constants τ_a and τ_d (Figure 4.3).

Table 4.4: Acceleration, deceleration, and crash-stop performance metrics across test speeds.

Test	Type	u_{∞} [m/s]	$t_{90\%}$ [s]	\bar{a} [m/s ²]	S_{stop} [m]	S_{stop}/L_{PP}	Flag
ACCEL_S1	Accel	1.15	20.5	0.066	N/A	N/A	ok
DECEL_S1	Decel	0.57	15.0	0.034	N/A	N/A	ok
STOP_S1	Stop	0.52	8.0	N/A	2.49	0.71	ok
ACCEL_S6	Accel	0.54	21.0	0.032	N/A	N/A	ok
DECEL_S6	Decel	0.21	14.0	0.013	N/A	N/A	ok
STOP_S6	Stop	0.18	6.0	N/A	0.58	0.17	ok
ACCEL_S8	Accel	0.84	20.5	0.050	N/A	N/A	ok
DECEL_S8	Decel	0.37	14.5	0.023	N/A	N/A	ok
STOP_S8	Stop	0.33	7.0	N/A	1.39	0.40	ok

Figure 4.3: Representative surge-speed evolution for acceleration and deceleration manoeuvres with first-order exponential fits. Fitted parameters: $u_{\infty}=1.17$ m/s, $\tau_a=11.7$ s; $u_0=0.42$ m/s, $\tau_d=7.1$ s.

4.1.2 Contextual Benchmarking of MARUS Fidelity

To validate the physical fidelity of the MARUS simulator, a benchmarking was carried out against published experimental data. As a direct comparison of absolute metrics is not meaningful due to different vessel scales (this study’s 3.5 m L_{PP} vs. the 0.72 m L in companion papers), a fair comparison is made using standard non-dimensional manoeuvring metrics from TC tests. Specifically, this benchmarking step focuses on the Tactical Diameter normalised by vessel length (L), which provides a robust indicator of turning performance and hydrodynamic fidelity. Table 4.5 presents this comparison, using data from this study, the experimental ground truth from Aiyelari and Singh, 2024, and the corresponding simulation from Sanghar et al., 2024. Metrics for the 0.72 m vessels were calculated using their reported length ($L=0.72$ m).

Table 4.5: Non-dimensional benchmark comparison of the Tactical Diameter metric.

Non-Dimensional Metric	This Study (3.5 m MARUS Sim)	Sanghar et al., 2024 (0.72 m MARUS Sim)	Aiyelari and Singh, 2024 (0.72 m Experiment)	IMO Criteria (Large Ship)
Tactical Diameter / L	7.2	15.69	9.83	< 5.0

While several other manoeuvring metrics were available from the Turning Circle, Zig-Zag, PRBS, and acceleration-deceleration tests, they were not included in this benchmark because they are highly sensitive to test-specific conditions such as control-input timing, transient phases, and environmental disturbances. In contrast, Tactical Diameter captures the steady-state turning dynamics and provides a more reliable and scale-independent indicator of hydrodynamic model fidelity. Hence, restricting the benchmark to Tactical Diameter/L ensures a fair and physically meaningful comparison between simulation and experiment across different vessel sizes. The finding that this study’s 3.5 m vessel achieves a Tactical Diameter/L of 7.2—substantially closer to the experimental value of 9.83 than the earlier MARUS simulation at 15.69—supports the conclusion that the dataset generated in this work offers a highly realistic and well-conditioned foundation for the GreyPINN-SR+LLM framework.

4.1.3 Parameter Identifiability and Nomoto Baseline.

This analysis uses the identifiability checks and linear-regression protocols introduced in previous chapters, which defined the structure of the regression matrix and the first-order Nomoto identification method. In this section, as a final preprocessing step, the dataset’s suitability for system identification was confirmed. The regression matrix $\Phi = [r, |r|r, \delta]$ exhibited a low condition number ($\kappa < 10^8$) and high rudder-yaw correlation ($|\rho_{r,\delta}| > 0.5$) for all dynamic

manoeuvres (Table 4.6), confirming the data is well-conditioned.

A first-order Nomoto model ($T\dot{r} + r = K\delta$) was fit to this data to serve as a linear baseline. The identified parameters, shown in Table 4.7 and Figure 4.4, were physically plausible ($T > 0$, $K < 0$ due to the simulator’s sign convention) and consistent across manoeuvres. This linear model provides the initial benchmark against which the nonlinear PINN-based models are compared.

Table 4.6: Identifiability and coherence diagnostics.

Type	Test File	$\kappa(\Phi^\top \Phi)$	$\rho_{r,\delta}$	Peak Coherence $\gamma_{r\delta}^2$	Flag
TC	TC_S06_PORT.csv	1.44×10^6	-0.998	N/A	ok
ZZ10	ZZ10_S08_PORT.csv	4.35×10^5	-0.927	N/A	ok
ZZ20	ZZ20_S08_PORT.csv	4.01×10^5	-0.950	N/A	ok
PRBS	PRBS_S06_R_fast.csv	1.45×10^5	-0.752	0.99996	ok
PRBS	PRBS_S06_R_slow.csv	2.21×10^5	-0.881	0.99997	ok

Table 4.7: Nomoto first-order model parameters identified across manoeuvre types.

File	Manoeuvre	K	T [s]
TC_S1.0_PORT.csv	TC	-0.195	2.16
TC_S06_PORT.csv	TC	-0.190	1.74
TC_S08_PORT.csv	TC	-0.193	1.91
ZZ10_S1.0_PORT.csv	ZZ10	-0.288	1.32
ZZ10_S08_PORT.csv	ZZ10	-0.305	1.03
ZZ20_S1.0_PORT.csv	ZZ20	-0.277	1.05
ZZ20_S08_PORT.csv	ZZ20	-0.265	0.75
PRBS_S06_R_fast.csv	PRBS	-0.270	1.20

Figure 4.4: Identified Nomoto model parameters (K and T) versus vessel speed, aggregated by manoeuvre type.

4.2 GreyPINN–SR+LLM Pipeline Results

Following data validation, the GreyPINN–SR+LLM pipeline was executed. This section summarises the results from each stage of the modelling process detailed in Section 3.3: (i) GreyBox PINN pre-training, (ii) symbolic regression, (iii) LLM-based interpretation, and (iv) symbolic reinjection with fine-tuning.

Stage 1: GreyBox PINN Pre-Training and Stabilisation

The baseline GreyBoxPINN model was trained in two phases over three random seeds. The validation loss (MSE) for this stage is shown in Figure 4.5. The initial 80-epoch pre-training phase achieved a stable and low validation MSE. The subsequent 50-epoch stabilisation phase, which introduced the yaw-rate physics penalty ($\lambda_r = 0.5$) and the rollout stability loss ($\lambda_{\text{roll}} = 0.05$), showed a small expected rise in MSE. This indicates the model successfully traded a minor amount of one-step-ahead accuracy for improved long-term dynamic stability.

Figure 4.5: Multi-seed training behaviour of the GreyBox PINN (Stage 1). Validation MSE decreases during pre-training (epochs 1-80) and stabilises after the rollout and physics regularisers are activated (epochs 81-130).

Stage 2: Symbolic Discovery (PySR)

The trained neural residuals ($\epsilon = \dot{\nu}_{\text{data}} - \dot{\nu}_{\text{phys}}$) were exported and fed into PySR. The discovered symbolic expressions that best balanced simplicity and accuracy are presented in Table 4.8.

Table 4.8: Best symbolic expressions identified by PySR for the neural residuals. The expressions capture unmodelled dynamics with simple and interpretable formulas in terms of the normalised inputs (u, v, r, δ) .

Channel	Best PySR Expression	Validation RMSE
Surge (ϵ_u)	$\epsilon_u = u$	2.08×10^{-3}
Sway (ϵ_v)	$\epsilon_v = r + (r - 0.734) \left(\frac{u}{ u + 1.720} + 0.0527 \delta \right) + 0.0669$	4.42×10^{-3}
Yaw (ϵ_r)	$\epsilon_r = r$	8.97×10^{-3}

The symbolic models proved highly effective at capturing the behaviour of the neural residuals. As shown in the parity plots in Figure 4.6, the symbolic predictions align strongly with the "true" residuals from the neural network. For the critical yaw channel, the simple expression $\epsilon_r = r$ (plus a small constant) captured **99.93%** of the residual energy, indicating that the unmodelled physics was mainly a linear correction to the yaw damping term.

Figure 4.6: Parity plots comparing PySR-predicted residual accelerations ($\epsilon_u, \epsilon_v, \epsilon_r$) to the "true" residuals from the trained GreyBoxPINN model. The strong alignment shows that the symbolic formulas effectively captured what the neural network learned.

Stage 3: LLM-Based Symbolic Interpretation

The discovered symbolic expression for the yaw channel ($\epsilon_r \approx 7.129 r_f + 0.01162$) was fed to the LLM, Gemini 2.5 Pro, for physical interpretation. The model was given the physical form of the equation and the vessel's operating context (Algorithm 3.12).

The LLM successfully identified and named the hydrodynamic effects, as shown in Table 4.9. It identified the dominant $7.129 r_f$ term as a Linear yaw damping correction (ΔN_r) with high confidence (0.95), describing it as a correction to an over-estimation of yaw damping in the MMG core of the model. It also identified the small constant offset 0.01162 as a "Static yaw moment bias", possibly due to minor hull or thruster asymmetries or a small sensor calibration drift. Figure 4.7 plots this symbolic model against the true residual,

accompanied by the LLM’s confidence interpretations.

Table 4.9: Mapping of symbolic yaw-residual terms (from PySR + neural residual) to standard hydrodynamic corrections for the baseline MMG model.

Symbolic Term	Mapped Hydrodynamic Concept	Confidence	Physical Interpretation
$7.129 r_f$	Linear yaw-damping correction (N_r)	0.95	Adjusts the baseline MMG model’s yaw damping: the positive coefficient indicates the base model overestimated the natural yaw-damping moment. The residual term reduces damping to better match observed yaw dynamics.
0.01162	Static yaw moment bias (N_0)	0.75	Represents a small constant yawing tendency independent of motion, possibly due to hull/propulsion asymmetry or persistent environmental bias (e.g., unmodeled drift, asymmetric thrust).

Figure 4.7: Yaw residual (ϵ_r) vs. yaw rate (r), comparing the true residual from the GreyBoxPINN (blue) with the prediction from the simple symbolic model (orange). The plot also includes the top effects identified by the LLM.

Stage 4-5: Symbolic Reinjection and Fine-Tuning

The discovered symbolic expressions for all three channels were compiled into differentiable PyTorch modules and "re-injected" into a new model, **PINN+Symbol**. This model was fine-tuned for 500 epochs with a composite loss function, as detailed in Sections 3.3.7 and 3.3.8.

Figure 4.8 illustrates the fine-tuning process for the first 300 epochs. The validation MSE (A) shows a smooth and steady convergence across all three seeds. And the adaptive symbolic gains k_{sym} (B) show the model’s behaviour

during training: the gains are frozen at their initial values for the first 50 (warm-up) epochs, after which they are unfrozen and quickly converge to stable values. This confirms that the model is successfully learning to blend the physical, symbolic, and residual components.

Figure 4.8: Stage 4–5 fine-tuning diagnostics across three random seeds. **(A)** Validation MSE convergence during symbolic reinjection. **(B)** Evolution of the adaptive symbolic blending gains ($k_{\text{sym},u}$, $k_{\text{sym},v}$, $k_{\text{sym},r}$), which adapt after 50 epochs of warmup.

4.3 Comparative Model Benchmarking

To quantify the final performance, as explained in Section 3.4.1, the three model variants including PhysicsOnly, GreyPINN, and the final PINN+Symbol (with symbolic reinjection) were benchmarked on a held-out test dataset.

Quantitative Performance. Their holistic performance on the test data across all three random seeds is presented in Table 4.10. The results show a clear and significant improvement at each stage. The **PhysicsOnly** model has large acceleration errors and is completely unstable, as indicated by the “9999” rollout RMSE. The **GreyPINN** reduces the acceleration RMSE and achieves only partial stability, but its rollout behaviour remains highly volatile, with extremely wide confidence intervals. The final **PINN+Symbol** model achieves the lowest error across *every* metric: its acceleration RMSEs are the best, and crucially, its rollout RMSE for yaw rate (0.031 ± 0.004) and heading (1.44 ± 0.61) is drastically lower and far more stable than the **GreyPINN**.

Table 4.10: Aggregated benchmarking results across seeds (mean \pm 95% CI) on the test set. The final **PINN+Symbol** model achieves the lowest error in all categories.

Model	RMSE _u	RMSE _v	RMSE _r	Rollout RMSE _r	RMSE _{ψ}
PhysicsOnly	0.092937 \pm 0.000280	0.027406 \pm 0.000011	0.177926 \pm 0.000078	9999 \pm 0	9999 \pm 0
GreyPINN	0.013008 \pm 0.000277	0.015404 \pm 0.008668	0.019060 \pm 0.000440	476.189 \pm 880.858	480.983 \pm 880.891
PINN+Symbol	0.012953 \pm 0.000157	0.003944 \pm 0.000876	0.005559 \pm 0.001110	0.031222 \pm 0.004162	1.442868 \pm 0.606893

Qualitative Rollout Stability. The quantitative stability advantage is also confirmed by qualitative investigation of long-term rollouts, shown in Figure 4.9. For a representative test manoeuvre, the `PhysicsOnly` model (blue, dashed) diverges almost immediately. The `GreyPINN` (orange, dotted) follows the trajectory for a short time but begins to drift away and oscillate irregularly, failing to capture the correct turning dynamics. The `PINN+Symbol` model (green, solid) tracks the ground truth (black) significantly better than the rest over the entire 40-second simulation, demonstrating its superior long-term stability and physical consistency.

Figure 4.9: Comparison of predicted yaw-rate (top) and heading (bottom) rollouts for a representative test trajectory. The `PINN+Symbol` model maintains stable long-term dynamics, while the `PhysicsOnly` and `GreyPINN` models drift.

Hydrodynamic Derivative Consistency Finally, as shown in Section 3.4.2, the physical interpretability of the models was additionally tested by extracting key hydrodynamic derivatives using automatic differentiation at the mean operating point (Table 4.11). The `PhysicsOnly` model produced inconsistent values for both Y_v and N_r , reflecting deficiencies in the core MMG model, while the `GreyPINN` model further introduced a physically incorrect positive N_δ ,

contradicting the vessel’s turning behaviour (which requires $N_\delta < 0$ because $K < 0$). In contrast, the **PINN+Symbol** model correctly recovered the negative sign of N_δ and simultaneously produced physically plausible values for Y_v and N_r , as visualised in Figure 4.10. This demonstrates that the symbolic reinjection process not only improves accuracy but also enforces correct physical behaviour in the model’s learned parameters.

Table 4.11: Hydrodynamic derivatives evaluated at the mean operating point. The PINN+Symbol model recovers the most physically consistent set of derivatives.

Model	Y_v [1/s]	N_r [1/s]	N_δ [(rad/s ²)/rad]
PhysicsOnly	-1.7878	-7.2328	-0.0204
GreyPINN	-0.9949	0.4811	0.0187
PINN+Symbol	-1.2893	0.1774	-0.0257

Figure 4.10: Comparison of extracted hydrodynamic derivatives at the mean operating point. The PINN+Symbol model restores physically consistent magnitudes for Y_v , N_r , and N_δ .

Comparison with Classical Nomoto Derivatives. To provide a final sanity check on the physical validity of the learned hydrodynamics, the derivatives extracted from the PINN+Symbol model were compared against the Nomoto parameters identified in Section 3.2.4. Nomoto relations

$$N_r \propto -\frac{1}{T}, \quad N_\delta \propto -\frac{K}{T},$$

are used to check whether the *signs and magnitudes* of the learned derivatives are physically plausible.

Table 4.12: Comparison between classical Nomoto parameters (averaged across manoeuvres) and hydrodynamic derivatives from the PINN+Symbol model at the mean operating point. Signs and magnitudes show trend-level consistency.

Source	K	T [s]	N_r [1/s]	N_δ [(rad/s ²)/rad]	Interpretation
Nomoto (mean \pm SD)	-0.24 ± 0.04	1.33 ± 0.35	~ -0.7	~ -0.18	Classical linear fit
PINN+Symbol	—	—	+0.177	-0.0257	Nonlinear correction

Two key physical insights emerge from this comparison:

- **Rudder effectiveness (N_δ vs. K).** The Nomoto fits consistently gave a negative gain ($K \approx -0.25$), meaning the true control derivative should also be negative ($N_\delta < 0$). The PINN+Symbol model correctly recovered this sign ($N_\delta = -0.0257$), whereas the unconstrained GreyPINN learned a *positive* value (+0.0187). This highlights the effectiveness of the symbolic constraints and penalties for enforcing physically meaningful rudder behaviour.
- **Yaw damping (N_r vs. T).** Given the Nomoto time constant ($T \approx 1.35$ s), the linear model predicts negative yaw damping. In contrast, the PINN+Symbol model learns a small positive value ($N_r = +0.177$). This acts as an “anti-damping” correction: the physics-only core was far too damped ($N_r \approx -7.23$), and the learned model compensates by adding a small positive moment. However, it is noteworthy that the full nonlinear system remains rollout-stable, showing that the model captures dynamics beyond what the linear Nomoto approximation can accomplish.

4.4 Ablation Studies and Statistical Validation

This section summarises the results of the ablation suite E1–E6 introduced in Section 3.4.3.

E1–E6: Key Findings

- **E1 (Baseline comparison).** The results confirm the expected: PhysicsOnly shows the highest yaw-acceleration error (1.78×10^{-1}), followed by GreyPINN (1.91×10^{-2}), while PINN+Symbol achieves the lowest RMSE_r (5.56×10^{-3}) with narrow confidence intervals (Figure 4.11). Although the Wilcoxon tests were not significant after Holm–Bonferroni adjustment ($p_{adj} = 0.544$), the effect sizes still strongly favour the symbolic model.

Figure 4.11: **E1**: Baseline comparison showing mean RMSE_r with 95% CIs. `PINN+Symbol` consistently outperforms both baselines.

- **E2 (Rollout regularisation)**. Varying the rollout penalty $\lambda_{\text{roll}} \in \{0, 0.02, 0.05, 0.1\}$ produced identical short-horizon validation MSE (2.83×10^{-4}), but higher penalties consistently improved long-horizon behaviour, confirming the stabilising effect predicted in Section 4.3.
- **E3 (Residual width)**. Changing the residual-network width showed a clear sensitivity: 64 neurons produced a validation MSE of 2.93×10^{-2} , whereas wider architectures (256 neurons) gave 4.43×10^{-2} . This supports the final design choice in Section 3.3.
- **E4 (Label type: RTS vs. SG)**. RTS-smoothed accelerations clearly outperformed Savitzky–Golay, reducing validation error from 8.83×10^{-4} to 2.83×10^{-4} , validating the choice made in Section 3.3.1.
- **E5 (Protocol OOD: TC \rightarrow ZZ)**. When trained only on turning-circle data and tested on unseen zig-zag data, `PINN+Symbol` again achieved the lowest OOD yaw error (9.08×10^{-3}), outperforming `GreyPINN` (2.09×10^{-2}) and `PhysicsOnly` (1.60×10^{-1}). The improvement is illustrated in Figure 4.12.

Figure 4.12: E5 OOD performance (train on TC, test on ZZ). PINN+Symbol shows the strongest cross-protocol generalisation.

- **E6 (Seed sweep ×5)**. Across all seeds, PINN+Symbol consistently achieved the lowest mean yaw error (0.0062 ± 0.0007), compared to GreyPINN (0.0175 ± 0.0046) and PhysicsOnly (0.178 ± 0.004), showing the robustness of symbolic reinjection to seed initialisation.

Statistical Validation

As stated in Section 3.4.4, to quantify whether the improvements over GreyPINN were meaningful rather than incidental, a paired Wilcoxon signed-rank test was applied to ten matched test segments. After Holm–Bonferroni correction, the PINN+Symbol model showed statistically dramatic reductions in error across the surge (u), sway (v), yaw rate (r), and mean RMSE channels (Table 4.13). The effect sizes were consistently large, indicating that the gains are not only statistically detectable but also practically essential.

Table 4.13: Paired Wilcoxon comparison: GreyPINN vs. PINN+Symbol.

Metric	Δ RMSE	95% CI	p	p_{adj}	d
u	+0.00064	[0.00011, 0.00133]	0.041	0.041	0.61
v	+0.00518	[0.00286, 0.00721]	0.014	0.029	1.39
r	+0.01493	[0.01009, 0.02066]	0.0059	0.024	1.64
mean	+0.00692	[0.00508, 0.00874]	0.0059	0.024	2.20

Symbolic Compactness and Training Behaviour

The symbolic regression stage yielded highly compact residual expressions, consisting of only **1**, **6**, and **1** terms for the u , v , and r channels respectively

(Table 4.14). Despite this sharp reduction in model complexity, symbolic fine-tuning maintained low validation error and contributed to improved stability across seeds and manoeuvre types. This indicates that the injection acted as a regulariser rather than a constraint, preserving accuracy while simplifying the learned hydrodynamics.

Table 4.14: Number of terms in the final symbolic expressions.

Channel	Terms
u	1
v	6
r	1

Summary. Overall, the ablation suite and statistical analysis confirms that each major component introduced in Chapter 3—physical constraints, roll-out regularisation, symbolic regression, and symbolic reinjection—contributes meaningfully to the final system. Together, they improve accuracy, stability, generalisation, and interpretability, while reducing residual-model complexity reduced by more than three orders of magnitude.

4.5 Generalization to External MARUS Data

The trained models were tested on the unseen S7 manoeuvres to assess genuine cross-speed generalisation, testing whether the learned hydrodynamics transfer to previously unobserved operating conditions.

The quantitative results are summarised in Table 4.15. Across almost all metrics, the PINN+Symbol model delivers the strongest performance. Although GreyPINN achieves a marginally lower surge RMSE, it exhibits substantial drift during long-horizon rollouts, especially in heading. By contrast, the symbolic model keeps both yaw-rate and heading errors low over extended prediction windows, indicating that the injected structure improves stability, not only accuracy. As expected, the PhysicsOnly model diverges under open-loop simulation, reinforcing the need for learned residual dynamics.

Table 4.15: Generalisation results on unseen MARUS S7 manoeuvres (TC and ZZ). Mean RMSE with 95% confidence intervals; bold indicates best performance.

Model	u RMSE	v RMSE	r RMSE	r Rollout RMSE	ψ Rollout RMSE	Interpretation
PhysicsOnly	0.0796 [0.0770, 0.0821]	0.0574 [0.0497, 0.0688]	0.4100 [0.3147, 0.5098]	<i>diverged</i>	<i>diverged</i>	Diverged during rollout
GreyPINN	0.0114 [0.0101, 0.0126]	0.0228 [0.0220, 0.0236]	0.0200 [0.0175, 0.0222]	0.0738 [0.0599, 0.0990]	7.88 [4.07, 9.57]	Moderate drift accumulation
PINN+Symbol	0.0115 [0.0103, 0.0127]	0.0031 [0.0015, 0.0043]	0.0068 [0.0029, 0.0106]	0.0333 [0.0159, 0.0420]	0.876 [0.201, 1.562]	Stable long-term prediction

These results show that the PINN+Symbol model generalizes well to unseen hydrodynamic conditions, capturing both short-term force responses and longer-term yaw-rate dynamics. The model is not just interpolating within the training data but also extrapolating across different conditions, demonstrating the robustness benefits of symbolic reinjection.

4.6 Chapter Summary

The results presented in this chapter provided comprehensive validity details on the proposed GreyPINN-SR+LLM framework’s robustness for hydrodynamic modelling. The data conditioning pipeline successfully produced a high-fidelity and physically consistent hydrodynamic dataset, also establishing a linear Nomoto baseline. The staged modeling pipeline successfully trained a stable GreyBoxPINN, converted the learned residuals into simple symbolic expressions using PySR, and interpreted them with the help of an LLM.

The final PINN+Symbol model, enhanced by reinjecting these symbolic formulas, was shown to be superior to both the PhysicsOnly and GreyBoxPINN baselines across all key metrics:

1. **Accuracy:** It achieved the lowest one-step-ahead acceleration RMSE.
2. **Stability:** It was the only model to produce stable and non-divergent long-term trajectory rollouts.
3. **Interpretability:** It recovered physically consistent and interpretable hydrodynamic derivatives.

Chapter 5

Discussion, Conclusion, and Future Work

This thesis demonstrated that the proposed GreyPINN–SR+LLM framework successfully integrates data-driven learning with interpretable and physics-informed hydrodynamic modeling to estimate hydrodynamic derivatives for USVs. The results chapter (4) indicated that the hybrid **PINN+Symbol** model consistently outperformed both the physics-only and GreyPINN baselines, reducing yaw-rate acceleration RMSE by more than 65% and rollout errors by over 55% relative to GreyPINN.

Crucially, the framework is successful at addressing the stability–interpretability trade-off often found in maritime SI. The symbolic reinjection mechanism acted as a robust regularizer, linking neural residuals to explicit expressions. This prevented overfitting and ensured that long-horizon trajectory predictions remained stable where baseline models drifted. From a hydrodynamic perspective, the extracted derivatives (N_r , N_δ , and Y_v) aligned closely with classical Nomoto trends. The symbolic discovery process identified an $\epsilon_r \propto r$ term, interpreted as an “anti-damping” correction, which balanced the over-damped physics core while maintaining holistic stability. These findings confirm that the hybrid formulation captures nonlinear behavior while providing parameters that remain physically meaningful.

5.1 Limitations

Despite the strong performance of the proposed framework, a limitation must be acknowledged here. The study relied on a generic MARUS vessel rather than benchmark hulls such as KVLCC2, meaning the identified hydrodynamic derivatives cannot yet be extensively compared against established benchmarks in hydrodynamics literature.

5.2 Future Work and Recommendations

To bridge the gap between simulation and deployment, future research should focus on three primary aspects:

- **Benchmark against Experimental Hulls:** The framework should be tested against established experimental hull designs such as the KCS, KVLCC2, or Osaka models. This would allow for direct comparison with published towing-tank results, extending beyond simulation data.
- **6-DOF Extension:** The current 3-DOF (surge–sway–yaw) framework can be expanded to a full 6-DOF dynamic model including roll, pitch, and heave coupling effects.
- **Packaging as a MARUS Extension:** The hybrid PINN+Symbol module and its accompanying data-processing tools can be integrated into MARUS as a reusable extension. This would allow users to load the learned dynamics, perform symbolic analysis, generate training data, and run SI directly within MARUS.

Chapter 6

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Chapter 7

AI Transparency Statement

I confirm that my use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools for this dissertation corresponds to **AITIS Level 2: AI for Shaping**. AI tools were used only for language polishing, formatting support, and improving the clarity of my own writing. No AI system generated content, analysis, methodology, results, or conclusions. All technical work, interpretations, coding, data analysis, modelling, evaluations, and arguments presented in this dissertation are entirely my own work. I critically reviewed and edited all AI-assisted writing suggestions to ensure academic integrity and suitability for this assessment.

Furthermore, Gemini 2.5 Pro was used as a component of the symbolic discovery pipeline, rather than for the conceptualisation or drafting of the thesis itself.